

SOLROUTES

GENOA
24 - 27
NOVEMBER
2025

INTERMEDIATE
CONFERENCE

Station 5.

*De-borderlands: naming, gendering,
infrastructuring freedom of movement*

SOLROUTES – Station 5

De-borderlands: naming, gendering, infrastructuring freedom of movement

Conference: Station 5 – De-borderlands: naming, gendering, infrastructuring freedom of movement

Dates: 24 – 27 November 2025

Location: University of Genoa, Italy

Type: Conference Proceedings / Working Paper Series

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18896238

Authors / Editors

Luca Queirolo Palmas, Dorian Jano, Enrico Fravega, Federico Rahola, Filippo Torre, Ismail Oubad, Livio Amigoni, Lülüfer Körükmez, Michela Lovato, Nadia Chaouch, Rassa Ghaffari

Design and Layout

Marzia Melone

Project Funding and EU Acknowledgements

Funded by the European Union (ERC, SOLROUTES, 101053836). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Recommended Citation

SOLROUTES Research Collective (2025).

Station 5 – De-borderlands: naming, gendering, infrastructuring freedom of movement.

Conference Proceedings. SOLROUTES Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18896238>

Copyright & License

© 2025 SOLROUTES Research Collective.

This work is licensed under *Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)*.

You are free to share and adapt the material with appropriate credit.

SOLROUTES

Foreward

We are so delighted to inaugurate, almost three years after the start of activities, this interim conference of Solroutes, a project acronym that combines the words solidarity and route and integrates them into a perspective, both scientific and political, of border abolitionism.

Over the last three years, we have trained ourselves as a research team and immersed in the landscape of impeded mobility with the aim of documenting and interpreting multiple ways of solidarities and resistance to border policies in a variety of contexts; in the heart of Europe, but also and above all at its variable frontiers, which are also shaped by EU externalisation policies: from Egypt to Mauritania, from Libya to Sene-Gambia, from Turkey to Tunisia and Morocco.

The conference we are opening today has three main objectives: the first is to discuss and connect the approach undertaken by the Solroutes collective with the experience of other researchers; the second is to create a common space for critical scholars in border studies to meet and exchange ideas; the third is to critically reflect on the methods and positionalities in ethnographic activism, that is, on our role as researchers as potential and ambiguous actors in the struggle for freedom of movement and social justice; also taking into account the possible encounters between social sciences and artistic languages in producing, supporting, maintaining and spreading an abolitionist imaginary within increasingly walled societies.

Shifting our gaze and our ethnographic fieldwork southwards has allowed us to question an established approach in scientific literature that revolves around the distinction between the political and humanitarian dimensions of solidarity. More recent studies also emphasise how both these dimensions – the political and the humanitarian – are somehow forced to converge and mix when confronted with a scenario of growing institutional hostility, which, in many countries, identifies migrants as a useful scapegoat and deploys the defence of national borders as a politically effective rhetoric.

According to this approach, however, solidarity becomes something external to the daily fabrication of illegalised mobility, separating in a Manichean way subjects and objects, donors and recipients, profit and non-profit actions, the West and the rest.

Moreover, let's keep in mind that these terms – route and solidarity – have been incorporated by the State thought into a framework of governance and control of migration: the route-based approach is conceived as a tool to act more effectively and timely to counteract inappropriate mobilities; at the same time, solidarity is evoked by Eu states to cope with "primary and secondary movements" and to "share the burden of asylum seekers".

The path we have followed unsettles this framework, also drawing inspiration from the genealogy of these words. The two terms 'solidarity' and 'routes', both of Latin origin - solidus and (via) rupta -, refer, on the one hand, to the dimension of the solidity, of unity and of being together; and on the other to the breaking down of a set of obstacles (solid themselves) as a condition for proceeding to a desired destination. In this sense, the route is always produced through struggles grounded in social intelligence and highlighting the strength that a group, bound by common interests or aspirations, can articulate.

Solidarity and routes, in their conjunction, can enlighten the everyday fabric of illegalised mobility through social relations of exchange, encounter, cooperation, mutual help and alliance between

travellers and non-travellers, migrants and non-migrants, enslaved and citizens, resonating with the historic North American experience of the Underground Railroad or the Caribbean legacy of maroons and escaped communities.

Thanks to our ethnographic encounters, we also tried to reframe solidarity not as an ontological property of a person (people showing solidarity versus people not showing solidarity), but as a contingent situation and a circulating energy, linked also to interested exchanges. In that vein, solidarity is not the product of already given subjects, but rather a relation that produces subjects. It can only be exercised, not possessed.

Solidarity evokes the idea of a solid matter that unites, even temporarily, to face a hostile environment, to defend oneself or to attack, to obtain something that is denied – (the same etymological root connects solidarity with “soldum” (coin) and soldier) –, and by doing so defines a perimeter, an outside and an inside, producing subjects who enter into a mutual relationship to articulate a claim: who is in solidarity with whom, to what extent, for what, until when? Within this perimeter, different activities take place: commercial exchanges, bartering, mutual help, care, and intimacy. Different social and cultural forms can be mobilised to produce, legitimate, and enact experiences of cohesion: family and parenthood, brotherhood and sisterhood, religious affiliation, self-racialisation, and the feeling of being part of the same oppressed social group.

In this perspective, we understand solidarity as a peculiar relation whose main outcome is to produce a route, a rupture, a crack across the border system. With the caveat that every form, every outcome, every structure is unstable and must be understood in terms of becoming. For this reason, we propose using present participles – infrastructuring, naming, gendering – to account for and explore the ambiguous and unstable nature of the social forms that emerge, examining the nexus between solidarity and routes.

Yet this instability can produce inhabited situations. As Martina Tazzioli suggested, abolitionism is not only about crossing a border but also about inventing new spaces and relations. We can draw a fertile inspiration thanks to the work that historians have done on marronage, the escape from plantations, the circulation of subversive information and ideas, “the common wind” to use Scott’s term, which during the 18th century linked the Caribbean with the other side of the Atlantic and the colonial empires.

The ephemeral maroon societies, although composed mainly of escaped slaves, brought together a plurality of subjects: sailors who had escaped from the chains of the ships and deserting soldiers, poor whites in search of freedom, fleeing from the law and from a marginal situation in Europe. Seen in this light, maroon societies were not a mirror of some African origin, but composite cultures built on encounters and merging. The processes of infrastructuring, gendering and naming, we suggest, can be explored in this conference, and they also evoke this type of abolition, highlighting the alliances during the journey that attempt to escape new forms of manhunt, which can generate a specific energy of solidarity, something that is neither political nor humanitarian.

Clarissa, a woman currently stuck in Libya, told us, for example, when we asked to help us find a missing person: “I posted her profile in dozens of groups in Tunisia, Libya, Algeria, Morocco... but nothing, no one has found her.” The negative outcome of the search, however, suggests a crucial dimension: the journey, precisely because it is prolonged, becomes inhabited, creating places of solidarity, often among anonymous people, and gives rise to a common wind of unsubordinate knowledge, somehow and somewhere able to counter the apparatus of capture and detention.

...Marroner/ Changing Route

Yet, some risks or limits still hang over our project. Something reductively violent or violently reductive in considering human movement, mobility and migrations as just experiences of crossing, basically borders. It is a perception that is amplified and fostered by several images and narratives reproducing, associating and representing "migrants" as people always on the move and always marching, in the act of going on and across, in the tragedy of a shipwreck, in being deported elsewhere or trapped within a detention centre. The very term migrant and the present participle it contains foster this perception, in the frozen image of a permanent act of crossing. We should find other words, more emic, so to say.

For the same reason, there is a certain unease in talking always of migrants and migration to address and define several heterogeneous experiences of human mobility and displacement that (particularly now), although not necessarily in flight, are increasingly linked with flight and escape, therefore not directly connected to labour mobility and circulation, nor to a deliberate choice.

These are two limits and two implicit critiques of our research and our narrow gaze. How to answer, or to deal with both of them?

As many Sudanese who escaped from Khartoum, and how Sarah, a young woman who fled from Gaza, told us in Cairo, where they all live and/in wait: leaving has been a decision, not a choice. But what kind of decision and what is behind it? How to realise and adapt oneself to such a decision to leave?

While taking into account the need for a broader idea of migrating than as a never-ending journey, one that is not only reduced to the act of crossing borders and traversing hostile territories, as well as of a broader word encompassing experiences of displacement that are not reduced to traditional ways of conceiving migration (be either economic and forced, an arbitrary distinction that selectively and partially tolerate the latter while criminalizing all the others), we do believe that human movement and displacement are always a matter of solidarity and of routes, of a materialistic way of reading and uttering the word solidarity and of a specific and enlarged idea of routes in terms of complex and multi scalar, material and immaterial, social and political infrastructures.

The call to "marronez vous" (by Aimé Césaire) was an invitation to flight, but it did not necessarily suggest a permanent movement; rather, to take a hazardous decision, to organize and to invent a different way to stay (free), and above all to live in a different way ("unavailable for servitude" T. Cade Bambara). Besides, it was also an exhortation to mingle, mix, blend, and thus to change. It evoked the search to build up a different space-time, collectively. And this is a matter of solidarity. And this is exactly what we intend for routes.

For this reason, we suggest adding two further qualities to these words (two predicates that, under the idea of infrastructuring, apply to both solidarity and routes): subaltern and abolitionist.

The first term comes from Gramsci and from the revisionist reading of his work made by a group of Bengali scholars (the subaltern studies) who suggested rereading the postcolonial transition of the Indian subcontinent from the standpoint of those marginal/ subaltern subjects (peasants) whose presence emerges only through the blank spots and white spaces of official colonial and national history. It is thus a story of an "un-civil society" (against the a-spatial and abstract Hegelian notion of civil society), a story of quiet encroachments as well as of violent uprisings (Guha, Byatt).

While talking of subaltern infrastructures, it should be useful to remind also Abdou Maliq Simone's idea of "people as infrastructures", as the expression of the specific "logistical counter-reason" (supporting all that is defined and conceived of as "bad/illegal circulation) enacted by the subalterns. From a subaltern point of view, infrastructuring is a matter of adapting, translating, transforming and finally inhabiting the forced times and spaces of a hostile environment that is directly or indirectly produced by borders regime, and also to reinvent both of them as a possible, subaltern "public spaces". It thus requires and promotes collective forms of cooperation and support, the production and exchange of specific and (under)common resources, knowledges, and languages. It requests the collective capacity to produce a different and impermanent space-time that is built up while is inhabited, as well as dwelled while crossed, since all these acts are not (chrono)logically separated in our practices and social experience, and they are often simultaneous, overlapped (Heidegger, Ingold). Indeed, the idea of route as a subaltern infrastructure and as a rupta breaks several other conventional distinctions, and above all, it extends, sabotages and subverts the logics of a corridor, suggesting a direction that is more political than merely geographical.

Subaltern infrastructuring entails the act of enrooting and radicating in temporary zones and shifting temporalities, mixing together roots and routes (Glissant), and enabling experiences of existence, permanence, mobility and resistance within an increasingly hostile environment. Can we define this idea of routes and of subaltern infrastructures as abolitionist?

Although not explicitly devoted to dismantling and abolishing the abstract notion and very existence of "a border" (and rather expressing the decision to stay in or move away from a place), at everyday level subaltern infrastructuring, as a way of producing routes and inhabiting im-permanent spaces, faces and counters the violent action and effects of a border regime, implicitly defying it and trying to subvert or at least adapt to its hostile environment. There is no clear abolitionist claim or project to be found here, but a lived, practical, maybe tactical or existential and implicit abolitionism. And it is a matter of reversing and subverting the blackmail of an immediate or remote "border" and the violent pressures it imposes, even by simply loosening its grip.

Abolition, as we know, is not just a matter of dismantling and erasing something (a border, a prison, a psychiatric hospital). It rather points to (collectively) producing something different (R. Gilmore), possibly the opposite or its reversal. It may entail affirming the right to stay and not to be evicted and deported, even when and where everything around them is violent pressure to circulate and move away. And it may instead affirm a right to move and cross when stopped at the gate of a border, surrounded by barbed wire, stuck in a detention centre.

As subaltern infrastructures that are built, crossed, and inhabited by "unwanted" and displaced people, routes are the different impermanent and transient spaces and temporalities produced at the crossroads by often forced encounters and silent encroachments. But they become abolitionist infrastructure insofar as they prompt a kind of convergence, an alliance, and a material solidarity that, at least temporarily, breaks any internal border and counters any external one.

And they can be everywhere around us, within a broader underground abolition geography. This is what we are looking for in our journey along solidarity routes.

Luca Queirolo Palmas and Federico Rahola

SOLROUTES

GENOA
24 - 27
NOVEMBER
2025

INTERMEDIATE
CONFERENCE

Station 5.
*De-borderlands:
naming, gendering,
infrastructuring
freedom of movement*

***WORKING
PAPERS***

SOLROUTES

Station 5.
*De-borderlands:
naming, gendering,
infrastructuring
freedom of movement*

WORKING PAPERS

NAMING

NAMING AND GROUNDING SOLIDARITY ALONG MIGRATION ROUTES

Nadia Chaouch, Dorian Jano,
Luca Queirolo Palmas, Filippo Torre,
SolRoutes Research Collective

INTRODUCTION

The SolRoutes project focuses on two terms – “solidarity” and “routes” – that are part of the linguistic and social heritage of the global North. Both of Latin origin (*solidus* and *rupta*), they refer, on one hand, to the dimension of the solid, of unity and of being together, and on the other to the breaking of a set of obstacles (solid themselves) as a condition for proceeding on a path or a direction. In their conjunction – solidarity and routes – they articulate a perspective that reads the production of undocumented mobility through social relations of exchange, encounter, cooperation and alliance between travellers and non-travellers, having as a reference and inspired by the historic North American experience of the Underground Railroad and later of sanctuary cities (Queirolo Palmas and Rahola 2022; Bauder 2017). During the first phase of the project, we also aimed to redecline solidarity not as an ontological property of a person, but as a situation and circulating energy linked to an interested exchange (Amigoni, Ghaffari, and Jano 2025; Bonnin, Fravega, and Queirolo Palmas 2024).

The terms “solidarity” and “route” are part of both the cultivated discourse—scientific and non-scientific—as well as the institutional and political discourse; in the latter, for example, solidarity is redefined as the necessary mutual aid between states *affected by inappropriate mobility*, while the *route-based approach* has also spread as a political-discursive initiative and approach in order to act more effectively and timely to counteract inappropriate mobility. From the perspective of the scholarly literature in Europe and the US, as we have repeatedly emphasised, the solidarity & route pair is framed – it is grounded – within two major discursive anchors that analyse it and from which those same practices derive legitimacy: the political (solidarity as transgression of the border regime) and the humanitarian (human rights as universal care and protection). On both the institutional and scientific sides, grounded in an anthropological lexicon, solidarity and routes remain broadly ethical terms that we apply to our fieldwork experiences, overlapping with the discursive practices of the protagonists of *inappropriate* mobility. Rarely have we encountered people on the road using these terms during our meetings and conversations, even though the dimension of mutual help and being together is at the core of their imaginaries and actions, which make it possible—despite everything—to cope with obstacles and continue or live through the journey.

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

Four main theoretical anchors guide our analysis.

a) Language constitutes social worlds.

The first anchor is the relationship between language and social worlds. Wittgenstein’s dictum “the limits of my language mean the limits of my world” (2016, prop. 5.6), positions vocabulary not as neutral representation but as world-making. Identifying the crucial words of inappropriate mobility makes it possible to trace the universes of meaning within which an experience is situated. Each semantic field opens distinct possibilities for action and solidarity.

b) “Parole” over “langue”: speech acts over language systems.

The second anchor follows De Saussure’s (2013) distinction between *langue* (language system) and *parole* (speech act), prioritizing subjective language production of language and its permanent re/de-construction.

The words narrating journey and solidarity emerge, die along the way, mingle with local lexicons, undergo invention and appropriation, incorporate pasts (customary, religious), shift in meaning while opening futural horizons of desire. This dynamism resists dictionary logic, demanding instead attention to semantic constellations where terms function as relational nodes.

c) Hidden transcripts.

Thirdly, drawing on James Scott (1990), we recognize undocumented mobility's vocabularies as *hidden transcripts*. That is, discursive practices concealing gestures and situations vulnerable to state sanction while simultaneously constructing collective identities and solidarities beneath surveillance.

d) Relational topology.

Finally, we assume a relational perspective, i.e. the possibility of grasping the meanings of solidarity and/or route from a joint reading of a space dotted with a plurality of emic terms.

The general aim is then to shift from the ethical to the emic perspective, decolonising and decentralising the discourse and the gaze on solidarity, while identifying the main terms that best describe, from the subjects' point of view, the social space of inappropriate mobility and the support relations that make it possible. This space can be delineated through the ways of naming the following figures and situations: 1) *the act of crossing the border or travelling*; 2) *the protagonist subjects*; 3) *the enemies*; 4) *the facilitators*; 5) *the spaces*; 6) *the circles of support*.

For each of these terms, we have aimed to:

- a) capture its meaning through its appearances in ethnographic accounts or other texts and documents;
- b) trace its genealogy, origin, and etymology, as well as its links with other social worlds close to or distant from that of inappropriate mobility;
- c) analyse its matrix of legitimation (religion, family, exile, etc.);
- d) identify its performative or future-oriented dimension.

In another research project, we collected the words and emic terms used by various social groups to discuss the violence at a specific border location, thereby forming a (partial) picture of the linguistic landscape around the Tunisian-Italian border (Equipaggio della Tanimar 2025). In this case, with numerous SolRoutes researchers dispersed across the Mediterranean, our aim is to connect linguistic repertoires that emerge from different social and cultural contexts, trying to identify which kinds of "family resemblances" (Wittgenstein 1986) can be traced among them.

First and foremost, we rely on a) research archives and interviews conducted across various fields; b) the ongoing conversation with informants we are in contact with; c) materials and texts through which migratory culture is conveyed (songs, proverbs, novels, etc.); d) scientific literature.

SOCIAL GROUPS ADDRESSED BY THE NAMING ANALYSIS

The case studies from which we collected words include fieldwork with specific and situated migrant groups, for the majority representing young and male social worlds, with the exception of Afghan and Iranian women and Palestinian families in Cairo.¹ Given the diversity of these populations and routes, we developed a comparative analytical framework to organise the emic terms collected across multisited ethnographic fieldwork within the social space of unauthorised mobility.

¹ This gender imbalance in our linguistic archive reflects broader methodological challenges in accessing women's voices along migration routes, a limitation we acknowledge and address through dedicated analysis in our companion working paper 'Gendering the Solidarity-Migration Nexus' (Amigoni et al., 2025), which foregrounds women's experiences of agency, waithood, and resistance across multiple case study sites.

a) West African male travellers who are irregularized across the Atlantic West-Med Passages and the Central-Med Passages.

Our ethnographic research, conducted between 2024 and the end of 2025, considered various groups *en route* to Europe via different routes: the Atlantic route (departing from the coasts of Mauritania, Gambia, and Senegal), via the western Mediterranean (departing from Morocco), and via the central Mediterranean (departing from Tunisia and Libya). In this context, undocumented movements are also connected to the need to accumulate economic resources by gaining access to several employment opportunities, from gold mining to fishing and agriculture. The groups we encountered during our fieldwork include different “ethnic” origins (primarily Bambara, Wolof, Lebu, Poel, Djola, Bameleké), linguistic capitals and religious affiliations (from Murid and other Sufi brotherhoods of Islam to various forms of Christianity); furthermore, in the relationships established through our research, the groups we studied are mainly composed of men. However, our interlocutors have in common – in addition to blackness and the inferiority to which it is subjected in the Arab world – a colonial heritage that makes French, ironically, a sort of Esperanto circulating within a subaltern linguistic community on the move, as they are in perpetual movement along the coasts of the Maghreb and West Africa in search of a passage to cross the European border. In this sense, the words we have collected about black people on the move through the Atlantic-West Med passages and the Central-Med passages largely delve into and retranslate the linguistic heritage of colonial French, sometimes blending it with local Arabic (from Hassaniya to Moroccan or Tunisian Darija), as well as with their own languages or those of other ethno-national groups, but also with Spanish and English.

b) Young Maghrebi male migrants along the Atlantic West-Med Passages and the Central-Med Passages.

The research has involved Moroccan and Tunisian single men using the Mediterranean sea as an entry gate to the European Union. The emic language to tale their adventure through the sea (or through the fences of Ceuta and Melilla) come from the Moroccan and Tunisian dialects; in some cases, there exists transnational words crossing all the Maghreb countries, or terms differ depending from the national and regional context of departure and transit. Specifically, we collected words used by Moroccans along the Atlantic and the Mediterranean routes (comprising the fences of Ceuta and Melilla) or Tunisian (would-be) migrants and deportees from the Mahdia region that aspire to reach Lampedusa by boat.

c) Moroccan migrants along the Balkan-Aegean passages.

From 2021 to 2024, we have conducted research from the perspective of Moroccan travellers across the Balkan passages. These travellers were mainly single men under the age of thirty-five, travelling in the lack of regular entry documents. We recognise that they depart from their countries outside any well-defined migration chain or system. Many of them conceive migration as a personal challenge, closer to a rite of passage than a collective enterprise, relying on connections and alliances built along the journey. In this context, we observed the construction of different kinds of imaginaries, lexicons, and representations depending on the spaces and local environments they traverse, through words coming from the Moroccan *darija* with a strong influence of French and Spanish languages, the languages of the former colonial powers and where the majority of Moroccan diaspora live.

d) Afghan and Iranian people across the Balkan-Aegean passages.

Much of the ethnographic work conducted in digital spaces and in concrete fieldwork for the Balkan-Aegean area has focused on Persian and/or Dari-speaking individuals from Iran and Afghanistan at different stages of their migratory journey. Persian and Dari are two closely related varieties of the same language, differing mainly in terms of pronunciation, vocabulary and certain grammatical features. Persian is the standard form, primarily spoken in Iran, where it is the official language. Dari, on the other hand, is one of the two official languages of Afghanistan and is widely used in government, education and the

media. While Persian-speaking communities are mainly found in Iran, Dari is spoken by large communities in Afghanistan, particularly among the Tajik and Hazara ethnic groups, as well as many urban populations. As a consequence, it is not uncommon for networks of people from Iran and Afghanistan to be on the move to coincide. Over the years, this has led to the partial sharing of not only routes, smugglers and facilitators, but also vocabularies, imaginaries and emic words. English has been somewhat received and integrated within this shared vocabulary, with words such as 'game' and 'jungle' becoming widely known and used. While a majority of male interlocutors have been observed in digital spaces, fieldwork in Greece has involved more Iranian and Afghan women. Individuals were of different ethnicities (Hazara, Kurds, Tajik, Fars) and religion (Muslim and Christian).

e) Albanian male migrants across the Balkan-Aegean passages.

The Albanian case study focuses on irregular migration via Balkan and internal EU-rope passages to the United Kingdom. We engaged with Albanian migrants who travelled via overland routes (Albania-Montenegro-Bosnia-Croatia-Slovenia-Austria-Germany-France-UK), sea crossings from France and Belgium, and occasionally used air travel with forged documents. Our fieldwork participants were predominantly young men under the age of thirty. Albanian mobility lexicons combine Balkan linguistic registers with migration-specific English terms.

f) Displaced Palestinian refugees along the Eastern African-Levant Passages.

The research with the Palestinian community in Cairo, started in February 2025, has involved several members of the wealthier segments of Gazan society who were able to pay the required sums to cross the Rafah border before May 2024 and seek refuge from the genocide by settling temporarily in some middle-class neighbourhoods of Cairo. Our main interlocutors were Palestinian families, students, and volunteers who sustain themselves through their savings or through informal work, often in partnership with Egyptian nationals, to cope with the lack of residency status. The Palestinian dialect is part of the Levantine Arabic, but the refugees' community in Cairo has adopted some words mainly used in the Egyptian dialect. So far, we have not been able to meet Palestinian evacuees who left for medical reasons; they do not have the same socio-economic stability, live in popular districts of Cairo, and rely on material assistance provided by material help.

RECONSTRUCTING THE EMIC TALE OF THE UNAUTHORISED JOURNEY

For every social group and case studies, we selected and regrouped the collected words used through six main positions and dimensions in the emic tale of migratory journey.

a) The act (of border-crossing) itself generates its own semantic universe distinct from actors, obstacles, or spaces. It captures the performative and future-oriented dimension of mobility itself, how migrants name the transgressive practice of border crossing as challenge, ritual, or warfare. Terms like *boza*, *the game*, *l-hrig*, or *aventure* don't merely describe movement; they construct subjects (*bozayeurs*, *harrāga*, *aventuriers*) and invite action.

b) The protagonist identifies self-naming practices that construct positive identities for interiorised and racialised subjects, avoiding reproduction of pathologising vocabularies. Self-designation terms like *musāfer*, *aventurier*, *soldat*, or *mohājer* reflect agency, enacting definitions of "us" versus "them," creating devices for collective self-recognition within solidarity networks.² Distinguishing how people on the

^[2] These predominantly masculine self-designations must be read alongside the empirical finding that women on migration routes often adopt different protagonist vocabularies, ones emphasising collective care, maternal responsibility, and resilience rather than martial heroism. The gendered asymmetries in protagonist self-naming are explored in 'Gendering the Solidarity-Migration Nexus' (Amigoni et al., 2025), which demonstrates how Afghan and Iranian women in Greece construct political subjectivities through feminist solidarity collectives like WISH (Women in Solidarity House) rather than through the ludic-martial framing of 'the game.'

move name themselves from how they name facilitators or enemies reveals the matrix of legitimation (religious, familial, heroic) they draw upon to construct dignity against victimising institutional gazes. The protagonist embodies positive self-representation, which is crucial to maintaining self-esteem and care within communities.

c) The enemies document how people on the move identify adversarial forces, both state actors and predatory individuals, within the field of forces that structures solidarity's circulation. Terms like *les arabes*, *badmash*, *commando*, *la-marin*, or *el hakem* reveal the border as battleground from migrants' perspective. These naming practices counter dominant narratives that depict host societies as "victims" of migration, instead showing how travellers experience militarised surveillance and racialised violence. Differentiating enemies from facilitators captures the moral economy of solidarity - who can be trusted, who exploits, who protects. This distinction is crucial for understanding *hidden transcripts* that shield practices from hostile actors while enabling cooperation with allies.

d) The facilitators map the migration industry from below, paid intermediaries and guides whose roles are ambiguous, neither purely exploitative nor altruistic. Terms like *ghachaghbar*, *rah-balad*, *cokseurs*, *samsar*, or *muharrib* employ metaphors related to logistics and transportation. Crucially, some terms (like *harrag*) designate both migrants and facilitators, revealing fluid boundaries and the phenomenon of former travellers becoming guides. Distinguishing facilitators from circles of support highlights the economy of solidarity, differentiating paid services from reciprocal aid, as well as commercial transactions from kinship obligations. This analytical separation reveals how solidarity functions as "energy and flow imbued with its own economy" rather than moral property.

e) The circles of support capture reciprocity and mutual aid systems based on kinship (real or fictive), religious brotherhood, and peer solidarity, the infrastructure of non-commodified support. Words like *fam*, *frères/soeurs*, *khoti*, *grands-petits*, *besa*, and *kanun* draw on metaphors of family reflecting segmentary models of mutual aid typical of family relationships, contrasting with paid facilitators' services.³ It identifies the inner circles of solidarity that can be mobilised for material and emotional support, the primary infrastructure enabling journey continuation. Distinguishing this from facilitators reveals different moral registers: familial reciprocity versus commercial exchange, sacred oaths versus contractual arrangements.

f) The spaces document how people on the move name the material and symbolic geographies where unauthorised mobility unfolds, spaces of concealment, waiting, danger, and social reproduction. Terms like *bunker*, *jungle*, *ghaba*, *musāferkhāna*, *zir abi*, and *tranquillos* employ metaphors of exclusion while also designating partial, yet symbolic, safe spaces. Yet function as crucial nodes in solidarity infrastructure.⁴ Spatial naming practices reveal how people on the move create cognitive maps of hostile terrain, identifying where to hide from surveillance, where to access resources, and where community can be temporarily constituted. The space domain encompasses the material substrate of solidarity, referring to physical locations where hidden transcripts can be safely shared and mutual aid networks can be activated.

^[3] However, the kinship metaphors documented here primarily emerge from male homosocial networks. Women's circles of support often operate through different relational vocabularies and practices — such as the WhatsApp groups among Sudanese women in Cairo ('Faisal women') or the horizontal feminist collectives in Greece analysed in 'Gendering the Solidarity-Migration Nexus' (Amigoni et al., 2025). Moreover, as demonstrated in 'Infrastructuring Solidarities' (Fravega et al., 2025), circles of support materialise through concrete economic practices: Senegalese tontines (rotating credit), Murid brotherhood houses in Mauritania, and Palestinian mutual aid associations in Cairo, showing how fictive kinship translates into material infrastructure.

^[4] Our linguistic analysis of space-naming complements the material ethnography of spatial production in 'Infrastructuring Solidarities' (Fravega et al., 2025), which examines how migrants physically construct ghettos, squats, and digital platforms as 'counter infrastructures' of reproduction and resistance. That paper documents how Palestinian refugees created 'New Gaza' in Cairo, not merely naming but materially building a landscape of cultural continuity through restaurants, shops, and community centers. Similarly, it analyses how Arabic- and Persian-speaking virtual platforms (Marino Dubois, Aegean Boat Report) function as spatial infrastructures enabling route navigation and collective mobilisation.

Crisscrossing the case studies with the categories and positions in the migratory tale, we developed the following table to highlight and understand the most significant terms appearing during our fieldwork.

Emic Lexicons Matrix: Domains of Solidarity & Route-Making

A semantic field map of emic terms mobilised by travellers across migration routes

ROUTE / POPULATION	THE ACT	THE PROTAGONISTS	THE ENEMIES	THE FACILITATORS	THE CIRCLE OF SUPPORT	THE SPACE
The Atlantic West-Med Passages: West Africans across Maghreb and the Atlantic Route	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> aventure boza se lancer, lancement (one gets on the boat and sets off) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> aventurier (risk-taker) les arabes soldat les hommes du désert Nous les blacks passagers 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> l'arab cokseurs camorassiens taximafia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> fam grands-petits frère-soeurs les étudiants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bunker maquis campo ghetto polo le village la forêt la placette tranquillos brousse jungle barzakh
The Central-Med Passages: Maghrebis along Mediterranean	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> harga/hrig (the burning) riski (hiding in a truck or ship) kharija (the exit) el hogra (humiliation/sociopolitical-economic conditions driving someone to take the risk) karama (dignity/honor and respect) hajja (escape) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> harrāga (the burners) el kharij (those who live outside homeland) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> la-marin (the navy) skadra (patrol boat) el hakem (the police) the state (the police state apparatus) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> harrag (the burner) samsar (the middleman) el harrag (the facilitator/migrant) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> drari (the guys) khotti (the brothers) comita (the inner circle) the family awled el houma (the neighborhood) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I-bahar (the sea)
The Aegean-Balkan Passages: Moroccans across Balkans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I-hrig (the burning) drba (the blow/the passage) taslima (the delivery) montaj (hiding in a truck) rihla (a trip/organized collective movement) al-hijra (religious/historical migration framework) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> harrāga (the burners) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I-grillage (the barrier) el-makhzen (the state) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> muharrib (the smuggler) harrag (the burner) samsar (the middleman) riberi (the smuggler) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> drari (the guys) khotti (the brothers) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I-ghaba (the forest) I-kamb (the camp)
The Aegean-Balkan Passages: Afghans/Iranians across Balkans & Turkey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the game (repeated attempts - forest on foot, facilitator-overseen taxi, ship concealment) geymzadan/geymwahal (to play the game/active participation in crossing attempts) guzara (waiting/killing time) khoda andaz (to throw oneself/self-initiated crossings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> musāfer (traveller) mohājjer/muhājir (migrant/refugee) malang (destitute/delirious person) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> badmash (criminal/hooligan) commando (army/police officer) reis (criminal boss/captain) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ghachaghbar/kachakbar/qāchāqbar (smuggler/trafficker) rah-balad/rah dawan (middle-men guides in border-crossings) jello-ro (one who goes ahead/scout) ham-rah (fellow traveller) 'mama'/uncle (smuggler-fixer) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> sarāf/hawala (transnational informal brokers/payment guarantee) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> musāferkhāna (travellers' inn/Caravanserai) 'Afghan Park' (migrant-named hub in Belgrade) 'jungle' (informal camp/woodland encampment) zir abi (underground route/underwater)
The Aegean-Balkan Passages: Albanian migrants' routes towards UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> kurbet/gurbet (temporary labour migration) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> kurbetli (the emigrant) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> polici (police/law enforcement) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vella (brother) shok (friend/companion) ndërmjetës (intermediary/middleman) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> kanun (Albanian customary law) besa (sacred oath/word of honour) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> kamp (camp) gomone (dinghy)
The Eastern African-Levant Passages: the Palestinian community in Cairo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tahreeb (smuggling of goods or people) Ghurba (the exile) Tanseeq (the "coordination") Sumud (steadfastness) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mtgharbiin (the exiled) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hala (Hala consulting and tourism) Nuzuh (the displacement) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hala (Hala consulting and tourism) Samsar (the intermediary) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fara3 hamoula (the branch of your family tree) 3ayla (the extended family) Usra (the nuclear family) 	

Note: Terms are organised by route/population (rows) and tale categories (columns). Each entry includes the emic term in its original language, followed by English translation/interpretation in parentheses. This matrix represents a partial and situated snapshot of living linguistic repertoires that continue to evolve along migration routes. It focuses on emic terminology used predominantly by male travellers. For examination of how women on routes construct different linguistic and relational repertoires of solidarity, emphasising collective care, maternal responsibility, and feminist political organising, see 'Gendering the Solidarity-Migration Nexus' (Amigoni et al., 2025). For analysis of how linguistic categories translate into material infrastructures of economic mobilisation, spatial production, and capital conversion, see 'Infrastructuring Solidarities' (Fravega et al., 2025).

FIVE OVERARCHING METAPHORS AND FAMILY RESEMBLANCES ACROSS ROUTES

The Table presents emic terms collected through multi-sited fieldwork, revealing both route-specific vocabularies and cross-cultural family resemblances in how people on the move name the social space of unauthorised mobility. These tale categories framework provides the analytical tool to recognise similarities and discontinuities as they are expressed through different languages and cultural logics. The framework enables comparative overview while respecting the situated nature of each linguistic repertoire.

What is evident at first glance is the arbitrary, partial, and situated nature of this table. As ethnographers, we decide which words are more significant and which are not, based on our research experience and immersion in the field. This table is neither fictive nor entirely real: it arises from the encounter between the researchers and the protagonists of migration.

In every research location, a rich and creative lexicon (a semantic field) exists that is used by targeted subjects to speak of the border regime, through a different language from the victimising and criminalising gaze of the States. The border is not only a system of rules that produces interdiction and obstruction; it also generates new meanings, new transgressive practices, new code words as alternatives to those of official institutions, and new appropriations of official or mainstream language.

It is impossible to produce a catalogue or collection of words used by different migrant groups. These words change over time (the terms used years ago differ from those used today) and across contexts (through interaction with local contexts). Instead, these words - and the social worlds they reflect - are intensely relational: the same meaning can be expressed through different words depending on who is speaking to whom. What we face, therefore, is not a catalogue or a dictionary collecting isolated words, but rather a constellation of meanings, where terms are nodes within a semantic field (Adorno 1997). These words produce forms of belonging and identity; they become metaphors of culture, something that is not fixed but relational and in constant change. However, in some cases, they can reflect a rigid sense of belonging to a specific social group.

After three years of fieldwork, we can state that in every border location or transit zone where we conducted research, each migrant group, to varying extents, produces its own *emic* and alternative language to make sense of and communicate about the marginalised conditions of movement as a reaction to border violence. At the same time, these words cannot be directly compared, as they emerge from very different cultural, religious, and social contexts. What we can do is to acknowledge that different kinds of metaphors and family resemblances can be traced among these terms. Words used to name the protagonists of migration can be grouped together because they draw on shared metaphorical frames.

Returning to the Table, we observe that:

a) metaphors of war and resistance. The border and the route is a *battleground* not only from the point of view of the border regime through narratives of invasion, hydraulic metaphors, and animalization of migrants, which depict the society of transit or arrival as a “victim” of migration in need of protection. In some contexts, migrants themselves see each other as *soldiers* that must have a military organisation (*commando, bunker, soldat*) as a form of resistance to police attacks and raids.

b) metaphors of challenge, success and steadfastness. *Boza, game, harga, riski, khod andaz, aventure* are all words that express a personal or collective challenge, a necessary effort to cross a line, a threshold, a frontier in order to gain success and become adults. The difficulties along the journey can be expressed through the natural elements where migrants live or travel (such as forests, seas, olive trees, and parks) or the containment spaces (such as camps and fences). These difficulties may be shared on social media as

necessary obstacles to achieving success, or omitted from the narrative to conceal the potential failures they represent. Interestingly, in the Palestinian case studies we did not find a word like *harga* with its implicit romanticisation of border crossers, while the main heroes are those who struggle to remain in the land to resist colonisation: probably here *sumud* has the opposite meaning of *harga*.

c) metaphors of family and kinship. The close circles of support along the journey are usually expressed through the metaphor of *frères/soers, mama, uncle*. This language reflects a system of mutual aid and support, a reciprocity and segmentary model typical of family relationships, which differs from the support received from intermediaries, usually under payment. In other cases, the family is the first inner circle of solidarity that can be mobilised to seek material support, especially in contexts with a long and stratified history of migration. Often, these family structures in migration are more fluid and flexible than one might think.⁵

d) metaphors of logistics and transport. A range of terms is used to describe the “services” provided by different types of facilitators, which tend to depict migrants as passive bodies to be delivered from point A to point B (*taslima, montaj, tahreeb*) or as customers buying a service (*passagers*).

e) metaphors of exclusion. Various terms express and reproduce a social stratification that emerges along the migratory journey. Words such as *ghaba, jungle, and camp* evoke the marginal living conditions in which irregularised migrants are compelled to live, or choose to live in order to avoid border checks, often outside what is considered the “civilised” world. More abstract words like *hogra* and *ghorba* express nostalgic feelings of alienation, humiliation and deprivation linking the psychological effects with the structural violence.

These words allow us to “see like an irregularised traveller”, offering the most immediate way to answer Khosravi’s question: “what do we see if we look at the border from the other side?” Their meanings differ radically from the criminalising or victimising gaze of institutions, NGOs, and international agencies.

^[5] However, naming and grounding alone cannot capture the full complexity of solidarity along routes. Our two companion papers complete the picture: ‘InHowever, our analysis of family metaphors here must be qualified by three important empirical findings from companion papers: First, family metaphors operate differently across gender lines. ‘Gendering the Solidarity-Migration Nexus’ (Amigoni et al., 2025) demonstrates how Moroccan mothers of missing migrants mobilise maternal identity as political legitimisation (‘I am a Moroccan mother’) to occupy public spaces foreclosed to other actors. Second, family networks translate into concrete economic infrastructures. ‘Infrastructuring Solidarities’ (Fravega et al., 2025) analyses how Murid brotherhood houses in Mauritania and Palestinian associations in Cairo convert religious/cultural kinship into logistical support systems. Third, family language can reproduce hierarchies. Both working papers note how gendered family roles (mother, sister, wife) simultaneously enable and constrain women’s mobility and political agency.

CONCLUSIONS

From this perspective, we view the language produced by the groups in motion, which we have accompanied with our ethnographic research as one of the different layers in a process of infrastructuring solidarity. Firstly, because the production of common words, a mobile common, enacts the definitions of an “us” and a “them” and therefore a device for the self-recognition of a collective in solidarity (in all its internal hierarchies) with respect to those who are not involved, in various ways, in the *game*, the *adventure*, the *boza*, or the *harga*. Secondly, because the counter-dictionary of the border that emerges from the set of metaphors analysed represents an often invisible and self-invisibilised device that allows its speakers to enjoy some right to indifference and to move across precarious symbolic safe spaces that attempt to neutralise the cognitive gaze of hostile external societies. Thirdly, because by avoiding the reproduction of a lexicon organised around the pathology and vulnerability of the migrant condition, subaltern linguistic production also reflects a positive image for inferiorised and racialised subjects, thereby reinforcing elements of care and self-esteem.⁶

As we have seen, following the materialist interpretation proposed here, solidarity is not to be considered a moral property of individuals but as an energy and a flow imbued with its own economy; in this sense, the flow of this energy needs a process of infrastructuring, however episodic and contingent it may be, in order to circulate. Subaltern language, in this perspective, is an element of this infrastructure, a crucial hub of shared knowledge that makes it possible to spread of practices of solidarity and mutual aid, while reflecting the varied field of forces within which it circulates, made up of facilitators, enemies and friends, allies, smugglers and predators.

^[6] However, naming and grounding alone cannot capture the full complexity of solidarity along routes. Our two companion papers complete the picture: ‘Infrastructuring Solidarities’ (Fravega et al., 2025) examines how naming translates into material practices—the economic mobilisation, spatial production, and capital conversion through which solidarity becomes operative infrastructure. ‘Gendering the Solidarity-Migration Nexus’ (Amigoni et al., 2025) foregrounds the gendered dimensions largely absent from our male-dominated linguistic archive, analysing how women’s agency, care practices, and political mobilisation follow different logics than the martial-ludic metaphors dominating our emic lexicon. Together, these three papers offer a multi-dimensional analysis of solidarity—linguistic, material, and gendered—advancing critical migration studies beyond securitarian and humanitarian paradigms.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adorno T. W. 1997. *Aesthetic Theory*, Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Amigoni L., Ghaffari R. and Jano D. (eds.) 2025. *Solidarity in Motion: Exploring Unauthorized Movements, Routes and Solidarity Networks across Europe at Large*, Genova: Genova University Press.
- Amigoni, L., Ghaffari, R., Körükmez, L., & Lovato, M. (2025) "Gendering the Solidarity-Migration Nexus", Solroutes Working Paper, November
- Bauder H. 2017. "Sanctuary cities: Policies and practices in international perspectives", *International Migration*, 55 (2), pp. 174-187.
- Bonnin I., Fravega E. and Queirolo Palmas L. 2024. "Of land and sea. Interested solidarities and the migration industry from below", *Mondi migranti*, 2, pp. 159-189.
- De Saussure F. 2013. *Course in General Linguistics*, Londra: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Equipaggio della Tanimar 2025. *Controdizionario del confine. Parole alla deriva nel Mediterraneo centrale* (a cura di Filippo Torre), Napoli: Tamu-Tangerin.
- Fravega, E., Ghaffari, R., Oubad, I., & Rahola, F. (2025) "Infrastructuring Solidarities", Solroutes Working Paper, November
- Queirolo Palmas L. and Rahola F. 2022. *Underground Europe: along migrant routes*, Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Scott J. 1990. *Domination and the Art of Resistance: Hidden Transcripts*, New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Wittgenstein L. 2016 *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus*, Asheville: Chiron Academic Press. Wittgenstein L. 1986 *Philosophical Investigations*, Oxford: Basil Blackwell.

SOLROUTES

The logo graphic for SOLROUTES consists of three overlapping, rounded, wave-like shapes in shades of grey, positioned below the text.

Station 5.
*De-borderlands:
naming, gendering,
infrastructuring
freedom of movement*

WORKING PAPERS

GENDERING

GENDERING THE SOLIDARITY MIGRATION NEXUS: THREE CASE STUDIES ABOUT AGENCY, WAITHOOD, AND RESISTANCE ALONG THE ROUTES

*Livio Amigoni, Rassa Ghaffari,
Lülüfer Körükmez, Michela Lovato*

WHERE WE START FROM: ABOUT OUR POSITIONALITIES AND THE URGENCY TO 'GENDERIZE' OUR GAZE

This working group begins from the acknowledgement that, during the early stages of its design and writing, the SolRoutes project did not explicitly incorporate a gender framework, which may have led to an implicit understanding of solidarity and (de)bordering practices as genderneutral. Similarly, migration studies have for a long time operated within a comparable framework, characterised by a predominance of genderblind research perspectives. This assumption, however, has been challenged by the project's rich empirical findings. Drawing on more than two years of collaborative research and field engagement across diverse contexts, the team's work has demonstrated that gender profoundly shapes how these practices are experienced, enacted, and interpreted. In other words, processes of migration, border governance, and solidarity are not neutral or universal; they are deeply embedded within gendered relations of power and inequality. This interest is derived not only from our position as feminist, decolonial scholars and activists, but also from our awareness of the dramatic neglect of women's and queer perspectives within the broader field of migration and critical border studies (Schmoll, 2023). Conducting sociological and ethnographic research with women as protagonists, rather than secondary voices, is in itself a relatively novel element within migration studies (Pinelli, 2019, Schmoll, 2020, Rigo, 2019).

The composition of our specific research group working on this axis is such that its members hail from a wide range of backgrounds and positionalities. These include an Italian man, Italian and nonItalian women, some with migratory experiences and others without. This heterogeneity has had a profound impact on our collective inquiry, giving rise to a dialogue characterised by not only productive tensions and moments of disagreement but also a profound recognition of how our identities inform our academic work. Ethnography requires those who use it to put their body and subjectivity into play (Semi, 2010). Douglas Ezzy (2010: 169), likewise, argues 'research is also embodied, emotional, and performed'. Some of us have experienced relatively easier access to both female and male spaces because, as various studies have noted, women are generally perceived as less threatening and may sometimes be granted greater access to people in positions of authority (RezaiRashti, 2013; Schwedler, 2006). Engaging with our differences has required us to confront the assumptions that underpin our perspectives, acknowledging that none of us can separate our research practices from who we are. Rather than seeking to eradicate these divergences, they are regarded as a vital source of reflexivity and intellectual richness within the collaborative process. Questions such as whether we should focus specifically on women, how to avoid a binary approach, and what it truly means to adopt a gendered lens have accompanied us throughout the entire process. It would be presumptuous to claim that we have reached consistent or definitive answers to all of them. Acknowledging the existing critiques and inherent limitations of this approach, we nonetheless collectively decided to focus specifically on women's experiences.

The migratory journey, whether directed to Europe or any other country, presents particular challenges for women, who appear to be affected in specific ways by the dangers of the route and the lack of facilities in countries of transit and reception. However, the women who participated in our research also demonstrate resilience and, in many cases, adopt their own strategies for coping with the insecurities of migration.

Much of the new research emphasised the independent agency of women in migration flows, contrary to the passivity implicit in previous portrayals of female migrants as moving in response to the migration of their menfolk. However, there is a paucity of rigorous analysis of the gendered experiences of migrants, which has led to the perpetuation of stereotypes of the 'dangerous' male migrant or the 'vulnerable' female migrant in both media and political discourse. In a parallel way, as Rigo contends, it would be equally fallacious to merely substitute this rhetoric with an emphasis on autonomy and the freedom of choice (Andrijasevic, 2014). Borders mirror the imperialistic genesis of the world order (Walia, 2013) and confirm its current postcolonial condition (Mezzadra and Neilson, 2013, Rigo, 2005). Borders do not function as linear boundaries that keep unwanted people outside. Rather, by assigning migrants to different legal, political and symbolic spaces (Rigo, 2007), they also hierarchize people's movement according to genderconstructed roles. Nevertheless, since the adoption of the Geneva Convention, the figure of the 'genuine refugee' – as the 'ambassador' of the Western World who fights against, or takes flight from, the threat to Western values – has always remained male.

Overcoming such stereotypes requires a more differentiated understanding of the experiences and needs of both women and men within migratory contexts, as well as an exploration of how gender relations are transformed throughout the migration process. As Cavounidis (2003) observes, the challenge is not merely to 'add' women into existing analyses or to pose the same questions to them that have historically been addressed to men, but rather to investigate how gender dynamics themselves shape and condition the migration and settlement trajectories of all individuals.

Moreover, it is evident that the discourse surrounding female victimhood, characterised by a lack of subjectivity and a perceived need for rescue (Mai, 2011), permeates legal discourses, numerous acts of solidarity, and our research endeavours. The notion of 'performing the border' (Wonders, 2006) is a complex concept that can be used to deconstruct, problematise and confirm gender roles and hierarchies, both from an institutional perspective and from the perspective of those who cross borders. Indeed, the women who cross the Aegean Sea in search of asylum, those who have settled in Egypt and those seeking justice in Morocco, force us to rethink unauthorised migration and asylum as a terrain of political struggle. This is because their acts not only contest the role assigned to them as gendered illicit migrants but also challenge vulnerability as a condition that diminishes their agency. In other words, their acts resignify the political function of refugee law beyond the scope institutionally assigned to it.

The concept of gendering the migration–solidarity nexus invites a systematic exploration of the ways in which migration and border processes, as well as the solidarities that emerge around them, are constructed and lived through gendered, embodied, and relational dimensions. This approach privileges women's perspectives and experiences, while simultaneously acknowledging that, as a relational concept, gender does not operate in isolation. Rather, it intersects with other axes of social differentiation—such as race, class, sexuality, age, and legal status—to produce a multiplicity of positionalities, vulnerabilities, and forms of resistance. Through this lens, migration and solidarity appear not as homogeneous categories but as complex, dynamic fields of negotiation that are continuously (re)shaped by gendered practices and expectations.

From this perspective, the concept of solidarity needs to be reevaluated. It is not an inherently genderneutral or egalitarian concept; rather, it is structured by the gendered norms and hierarchies that inform social interactions and institutional arrangements. Gender influences the formation, maintenance, and constraints of support networks, whether these take shape in informal contexts among migrants or in formal organisational and humanitarian settings. Within these spaces, relationships of care, protection, and assistance can both reproduce existing hierarchies and challenge or subvert them. Solidarity, therefore, emerges as a contested terrain in which power, emotion, and political commitment intersect.

By foregrounding gender as a constitutive rather than peripheral dimension of migration and solidarity, this research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of how power operates across borders and within practices of mobility and survival. It highlights how gendered dynamics shape the very possibility of solidarity, revealing the complex interdependence between migrating, belonging, and justice in contemporary border regimes. Drawing on these reflections, this presentation aims to highlight several underappreciated aspects of the experiences of women who, in various ways, have navigated migratory trajectories. The analytical trajectory we propose follows an intertwined spatial and temporal path, encompassing different moments and sites of women's migratory lives. This multiscalar perspective allows us to examine how gendered forms of solidarity and vulnerability are articulated across distinct yet interconnected phases of migration.

As a first case, the research investigates how migration affects those left behind in countries of origin, examining the mobilisation of mothers of missing migrants in **Morocco** and the involvement of these women in organising mutualaid and solidarity networks. The second spatial and temporal dimension focuses on the lived experience of mobility itself — confronting irregular border crossings and negotiating daily survival in those countries identified by women as intermediate spaces of transit before continuing their journeys. The structures and implications of waiting are not gender neutral either, with Auyero (2020) arguing that it shares many of the traits of male domination. It is these understandings of waiting, as an element of the migration system design with explicitly racialised and gendered productions and consequences, that the second and third sections further (O'Donnell, Ridgway & Jelinic, 2025). The stories and experiences of selforganised collectives of migrant women in **Greece** are discussed as case studies that reveal the creative and emancipatory forms female solidarity can assume while still on the move. As a third case study, the research investigates how social expectations, assigned responsibilities, and gender roles shift in situations of displacement in **Egypt**. It focuses on how Sudanese youth experience and negotiate gender and migration, exploring how these dynamics affect their integration into new settings.

CASE STUDIES

IN THE COUNTRY OF ORIGIN. FAMILY MOBILISATION FOR BORDER DISAPPEARANCES IN MOROCCO

The mobilisation of families of missing migrants in Morocco offers a compelling lens through which to explore how unauthorised migration affects not only those in transit, but also the social and affective fabric of communities in countries of origin. Drawing on ethnographic research conducted by the Morocco Antenna within the Solroutes project, we start our analysis by reflecting on how the materiality of the border—in the specific experience of a border disappearance —penetrates the everyday lives of those left behind, activating sociopolitical dynamics that reshape traditional gendered structures of intimacy, kinship, and public engagement.

When someone disappears at the border, those left behind must confront the weight of their loved one's absence (Edkins, 2011; Huttunen, 2025), an experience that reverberates across multiple dimensions of family and social life. In everyday experience, the relationship with the disappeared persists, amid confusion and ambiguity about their fate (Boss, 2009; Kovras and Loizides, 2011). Families find themselves facing as well a series of economic problems when the missing person was a source of support for the family (Robins, 2022); intimate and social relational reconfigurations, for example when women are left alone to manage the household economy (Zia, 2019; Menin, 2017); bureaucratic and administrative obstacles linked to the uncertainty of the missing person's status (Ferrándiz and Robben, 2015); and profound social and intimate disruptions, in which relationships are reconfigured around the disappearance (Edkins, 2011;

Huttunen and Perl, 2023). This reflection focuses specifically on the female dimension, examining how the experience of loss has triggered processes of negotiation, instrumentalization, and at times subversion of gender roles. The aim here is not to provide an exhaustive analysis of the phenomenon; rather, we share a situated reflection on specific elements related to gender and the politicisation of gender identities within the context of unauthorised migration. The theoretical frameworks presented focuses on the politics of appearance and performance studies (Butler, 2015; Arendt, 1958; Rancière, 1999) and with scholarship on disappearance and truthseeking mobilisations¹ (Huttunen and Perl, 2023; Menin, 2017; Zia, 2019), to examine how border violence reverberates through families, in particular looking at how the gender identities of sisters and mothers—socially constructed through their relationships with men—are simultaneously mobilized, negotiated, and subverted by women who resist border violence.

Within this context, 15 months of fieldwork in Morocco allowed to engage with ten Moroccan families who experienced the disappearance of a loved one at the border, to observe the practices, relationships, and dynamics through which the demand for truth becomes a political matter. The positionality of our field researcher—a young white woman with basic knowledge of Arabic—shaped these encounters, facilitating access to intimate family spaces and enabling relationships, particularly with Moroccan women, while inevitably influencing the dynamics of expectations, trust, and disclosure. In analysing how the intimate experience of disappearance translates into a politicisation of lived experience, we focused on public memory practices and mobilisations, where the gender dimension emerged as an unavoidable and central element that necessarily shaped the analysis. The families we worked with come from both rural and urban contexts, belonging primarily to subaltern classes; most had no prior experience with organised activism. All documented disappearance cases concern men aged between seventeen and forty, while among family interlocutors, the composition is more diverse: mothers, fathers, sisters, and brothers aged approximately between thirty and sixty years old.

Mobilisation for border disappearances must therefore be read at the intersection of gender and class: people from subaltern backgrounds, particularly women, now occupy politically significant public spaces, transforming personal loss into collective action. The public mobilisations of relatives of missing migrants in Morocco show how border violence and disappearance produce new political subjectivities grounded in family ties, gendered roles, and affect. In the ethnographic cases observed, collectives composed primarily of women² were involved, united by the experience of a loved one's disappearance at the border. During public and private meetings, it has been possible to observe how family members strategically deploy family ties as a source of political legitimation. To underline this point, we share a significant moment from the ethnographic fieldwork, concerning a public meeting in Rabat between institutional actors, civil society representatives, and relatives of missing migrants on the topic of border disappearances. On that occasion, families from various cities in Morocco participated and were among the first to speak. They introduced themselves by describing their relationship with the missing person. For example, one woman began by introducing herself by name and adding, "I am a Moroccan mother"; the second simply said, "I am here for my son, who disappeared ten years ago." She then passed the microphone to the woman sitting next to her: "I am a mother and I am looking for my son who disappeared on October 15, 2023;

¹ In Morocco, mobilizations for border disappearances are part of an activist tradition rooted in movements for the mukhtafyn (the disappeared) during the "years of lead" under Hassan II's regime (Biondi 2025; Menin, 2017). Even then, women – primarily mothers and wives – played a central role in organizing and leading public protests to demand truth and justice for their missing loved ones.

² In the ethnographic cases proposed here, women present and represent themselves as a collective; accordingly, the text treats them as a collective female subject engaging with public space. While differences among participants—such as class, geographic origin, and social capital—are acknowledged, this contribution does not pursue a systematic intersectional analysis of those divergences. The approach adopted here privileges collective practices and the ways relational identities (mother, sister) are publicly mobilized, leaving comparative and intersectional investigations of socio-economic, territorial, and generational variations to future research.

I want to know what happened to him.” Another said, “We are here to make our children's voices heard. There are only a few of us here today, but we are the voice of everyone. My son disappeared in August 2021, and I still have no news.” And so on. They held in their hands photographs of their loved ones, lifting them as they spoke; the portrayed faces, young and sometimes smiling, remained visible to the audience. By presenting themselves publicly through their relationship with the disappeared rather than through names and personal details, they claim what Zia (2019) defines as affective law: a system of sociopolitical practices that draws legitimacy from the bond of loyalty to loved ones, in contrast to governmental law.

In their public demands, they mobilise themes from the familial sphere—suffering, disorientation, care—extending them into the political sphere and making their presence in otherwise foreclosed spaces socially acceptable. The emotional repertoire is here mobilised as an affective political language, rendering the relatives' position socially acceptable and justifying their presence in otherwise inaccessible spaces. On another occasion, for example, a group of families of 51 missing people demonstrated in front of the Spanish consulate in Agadir, and a woman shouted into the megaphone:

“We want to know the situation of our sons; we want to know if they are alive or dead. (...) We are suffering. Now we live on the streets, sleeping in stations outdoors. We have left our homes and our children alone. Long live the king. We ask him to help us find our children; they are all still very young”. (Fieldnotes diary, September 2024).

In this protest, the families' demands are expressed in moderate tones and placed within a culturally legitimate register: appeals to central authority (“long live the king”) are followed by emphasis on the suffering that mothers experience for their children. These invocations are part of an ongoing negotiation with power, oscillating between conformity and criticism, humanitarian appeal and political accusation. On the other side, in fact, maternal suffering is mobilised as well as moral legitimation to confront the authoritarian power in Morocco. For example, one woman described a police repression in these terms:

“A policeman came and pushed a mother, she who was already suffering the torments of hell for the loss of her son. She was crying and shouting: “I want my son, bring him back to me, help me find him!” She was asking for support, but the police came and pushed her, without caring about her feelings and her suffering. They had no respect for her pain”. (Interview with A., June 2024).

By stressing their positions as mothers suffering for their children, they thus construct a socially acceptable and morally legitimised activist identity that stands in opposition to the “spectacle of disappearance” (Zia, 2019). In this way, women's participation constitutes a form of gendered resistance (Menin, 2017; Zia, 2019). Less repressible than men in public Moroccan space, women draw on culturally accepted positions to enter a sphere traditionally gendered, blurring the boundaries between the domestic and the political and transforming roles of care into acts of dissent. The intimate experience “disturbed” by disappearance (Huttunen and Perl, 2024)—marked by prolonged waiting, uncertainty, and the haunting absence of the missing—becomes political when it moves beyond domestic confines into the public sphere. Through search practices, sitins, and demonstrations, families of missing migrants socialise their grief and the memory of their loved ones. Scenes such as mothers gathering to throw flowers into the sea at the Algerian border or protesting in front of the Spanish consulate and the Moroccan Ministry of Foreign Affairs, reconfigure these individuals as political subjects. By narrating their loved ones' stories, asking questions, and demanding truth and justice, they position themselves as interlocutors visàvis institutional actors, despite lacking prior political experience. By leaving their homes to physically occupy typically masculine spaces—streets, squares, institutional sites—they create what Arendt (1958) defines as “spaces of appearance” and claim the right to appear (Butler, 2015): their own, as political subjects, and that of their missing loved ones. As Rancière states, a gesture is political when it “moves a body from the place assigned to it” and “makes visible what had no business being seen” (1999: 28–30).

Finally, these practices configure a “politics of reappearance” (Huttunen and Perl, 2025) in which relatives mediate the political presence of the disappeared. When they declare “We are here to make our children’s voices heard,” when they raise photographs during protests, when they repeatedly recount stories in public spaces, they enact a collective performance that restores presence to those who have been disappeared. The haunting presence of the disappeared in domestic spaces is transformed into a political presence in public spaces, now haunting the institutions called to account for their absence.

Importantly, such transformations are not limited to stationary contexts. As the following section illustrates, migration introduces new constraints and possibilities; yet, women migrants similarly appropriate gendered expectations of care to articulate resistance, demonstrating the portability and adaptability of these practices.

ON THE MOVE. GREECE

This paragraph employs a transfeminist and postcolonial approach to enhance a perspective that is frequently marginalised within the field of migratory studies: the experience of selforganisation and solidarity of women on the move. Indeed, while the number of women on the move towards, around and across Europe has constantly been on the rise, there has been a dearth of attention paid to the gendered nature of unauthorised migration (Freedman, 2016). When such attention has been paid, it has focused predominantly on the aspects of violence, suffering, and passivity. In contrast to this prevailing trend, this section pays attention to the practices and networks related to informal cooperative actions that could fall under the terms ‘migration industry from below’ and ‘interested solidarity’ (Bonnin et al., 2024) underpinning women’s unauthorised movements along the Balkan Route and in Greece specifically, with a focus on Iranian and Afghan flows. Afghan and Iranian women migrating to Greece often describe themselves as caught in a condition of multiple marginality; they constitute a vulnerable group within the overall migrant population. The absence of comprehensive immigration policy, the prevalence of undocumented work, and spatial and social isolation, inconjunction with prejudiced perceptions regarding women’s capacity for collective action, contribute to the perception that these women are unable to engage in proactive, organisational, entrepreneurial and solidarity activities (Christopolou and Leontsini, 2017). Consequently, these aspects remain mostly understudied. Indeed, this research illuminates the creative and numerous strategies that women on the move have developed to navigate the various social, economic, and racialised spaces created within their migration experiences. The findings show how a powerful will to navigate through various legal systems leads to the emergence of political subjectivities along the way (Khosravi, 2020).

“Women here have shown much more resilience than men”, an interviewee commented; “when Moria burnt down, many men fell into desperation, depression and even addiction; women did roll up their sleeves and moved on” (interview, 27/11/2024).

The ‘feminisation of migration’ is a concept that facilitates understanding and visibility of the problems encountered by women in the migration process. As actors primarily positioned at the centre of migration, women play a significant role in enabling themselves and other individuals migrating with them to sustain themselves, shouldering considerable responsibilities from the initial to the final stages of the process (Avcil 2021). Contrary to the notion of being passive actors, women from Afghanistan and Iran have been shown to take an active role in their own migration, often acting autonomously in decisionmaking processes. This includes their choice to leave their country of origin, as well as those of transit, and the routes to undertake.

These women have demonstrated a commitment to being involved in the decisionmaking process throughout their journey, often working to fund their travels and support their families. This commitment is evident even in the context of asylum processes, where they have been known to devise innovative strategies for financial sustainability. Accumulation of various forms of capital, such as cultural (language proficiency, education), legal (residence permit, passport), and economic (a job, salary), is only possible when one remains in one place for a prolonged period. In her study of waiting and uncertainty experienced by refugees in transit, Massa (2020) correctly states that immobility and prolonged waiting between one border crossing and the next do not imply passivity. Other scholars engage a gendered lens in their examination of migration and mobility to highlight how 'staying put' is imbued as passive and coded in feminised ways (Conlon, 2011). For example, Hyndman and Giles (2011) distinguish between waiting in refugee camps in the Global South, a feminised practice associated with passivity and helplessness, in opposition to refugees in the Global North who are masculinised and viewed as a threat. Immobilised and waiting migrants are actively trying to turn obstacles into opportunities and to mobilise their resources to improve their situation. Mobility and immobility, thus, do not need to be in binary opposition to one another.

WISH—Women in Solidarity House, is a feminist selforganised collective of former and current women on the move born in Lesvos. It is defined by the words of one of its members as a collective to *"resist and struggle together to build networks of trust, support and care: we are women who do not need NGOs and men"* (12/11/2024). Solidarity represents a pivotal instrument utilised by the collective to assist members in their resistance, education, and enhancement of their circumstances. The collective functions on a horizontal basis and is comprised of women who have experienced unauthorised migration to the island, are still on the move or, for a variety of reasons, live there permanently. The women have various geographical backgrounds, including those from Afghanistan, Iran, Congo, and European nations. The collective arranges a variety of events, including fundraisers, solidarity parties, film screenings, women's assemblies, and daily trips, with the objective of advocating for and supporting individuals subjected to detention under migration policies. Most importantly, it provides a safe space for its members to seek help and support for anything related to their experiences as former or current women on the move. The political basis of the collective work is evident: in a context characterised by the hegemony of *"NGOs managed almost exclusively by white people"* (interview, 12/11/2024), WISH considers solidarity and selforganisation to be *"the best tools to change the system in which we are trapped"*; in this particular context, the collective bears relevance as it is a significant expression of the need that subaltern actors, such as LGBTQI+ and women on the move, feel to selforganise and manage their experiences collectively, outside the humanitarian machine that permeates the island and monopolises all practices pertaining to solidarity towards migrants.

Alongside more structured realities such as WISH and some other informal spaces, we find everyday informal (micro)solidarity practices, defined as *"those manifestations of mutual or unilateral help or support that do not happen in formal contexts and mostly remain hidden from public view because they take place at smaller scales and involve a limited number of people"* (Cuttrita, 2025). As Dinçer (2025) similarly observes among Iranian women refugees in Turkey, solidarity practices among women are not limited to just sharing lived experiences: they also share more material and practical information to help them survive within the asylum regime. Multiple volatile yet significant instances of collaboration and mutual aid that were distinctly femaleled can be traced in the Greek islands analysed in the current study; in some spaces exclusively frequented by women, it was customary to engage in the exchange of information such as the most reliable smugglers to facilitate the continuation of their journey, the arrival of the different Game from Turkey, the location of basic services on the island, and the organisation of activities just for women, like a day of fishing reserved for women only. Access to information is the recurring motif in all attempts at networking and gathering among migrant women; it seems to regulate the deployment of agency and

the ability to model the mobility narrative; in an informal place run jointly by Persian-speaking volunteers, refugees and asylum seekers, it has become customary to organize informative sessions about the perils and challenges of migration for women specifically. The guidance is imparted by women to women, rather than being disseminated by a volunteer or activist and, most significantly, by women who, like the women to whom it is addressed, have already crossed a border and achieved a positive outcome. The tips are simple, concrete, and specifically designed for a female audience that is not idealized and which, in this case, is not particularly educated. Rhetorical buzzwords such as 'empowerment' and 'agency' are absent, but the advice is imbued with all its concrete meaning. The meetings create a space characterised by solidarity and the sharing of experiences, where women with similar migratory backgrounds can confront and provide mutual support.

As has been demonstrated, informal solidarity is typically characterized by its voluntary nature; nevertheless, it may encompass economic transactions or the exchange of interests. While formal solidarity is best exemplified by the various forms of support provided by IOs or humanitarian NGOs, mostly within the formal framework of specific projects supported by various funding sources, informal solidarity is more likely to emerge as mutual assistance within migrant groups in the process of making their way towards Europe. Drawing on Richards and Lundahl's (2021) notion of waiting collectively, we understand the shared experience of waiting as a relational practice that subverts the temporal regime imposed by border control. In contexts where mobility is suspended and time becomes a tool of governance, the act of waiting together becomes more than a passive condition—it transforms into a form of solidarity and subtle resistance. By reclaiming and using time collectively, migrants and their allies create spaces of mutual recognition and care that challenge isolation and depoliticization. Solidarity, in all its manifestations, thus emerges as a relational practice that contests both the fragmentation and alienation produced by border regimes, while generating alternative temporalities grounded in coexistence, endurance, and collective presence.

WAITING IN A NEIGHBOURING COUNTRY. THE CASE STUDY OF SUDANESE WOMEN IN CAIRO

The paragraph explores how societal expectations, task assignments, and the roles evolve in the context of displacement. In particular, the aim is to investigate how Sudanese youth navigate the intersection of gender and migration—how both genders perceive their roles and how these perceptions influence their adaptation to new environments.

One of the critical questions emerging from fieldwork concerns the way young, highly educated Sudanese individuals have managed to create escape routes out of Sudan. Did they rely on preexisting networks of relationships to facilitate their journey, or did they have to quickly build these connections as they fled? It is striking how many of these individuals appear to have created escape routes almost overnight—through friends, family, or even strangers who became essential lifelines. These individuals, often in moments of extreme urgency, must adapt quickly, forging new networks and relationships while remaining prepared to move at a moment's notice. This leads to the exploration of the emotional and psychological dimensions of migration. Upon arriving in a new city like Cairo, Sudanese migrants are not only physically displaced but also forced to reinvent their lives. While exact numbers are unavailable, sources and informants indicate that hundreds of thousands of women make up the majority of those arriving in Egypt, alone and often with parts of their families. The reality encountered revealed a notable shift in demographic patterns, with a growing number of women and children moving. This increase is directly linked to the spread of the ongoing conflict in Sudan, which has forced many families to flee Khartoum and many other cities in search of safety.

"I arrived in Egypt in mid of July, two months after the war. My mother and siblings, we came by car, they took us directly from our home and we arrived here. It is difficult now because yes we left but other relatives are still there, my grandmother, aunt, uncle, big brother. - We chose Egypt cuz we came here regularly. Two years ago we were here for a holiday. We came maybe ten times, we know Egypt very well, culture is similar and also not very expensive for us, the language is the same, we came also to treat my father, for medical reasons. The rest of the family is Ombdurman, it's a month that we cannot even communicate, there isn't still the internet. We support them, we send money from here because at the moment it is not possible to work in Sudan, my mother is a teacher, there are many Sudanese schools here in Cairo. For Sudanese, it is not easy in Egyptian school, to be integrated well. I would have not come here for living if the war didn't start, even if I came many times in the past was different, I see that Egyptian treat us differently now, before they were very nice, generous, now is completely different, it upside down, because we they think we come from war and we are broke, they are afraid we don't pay rent. Many people, especially men came here and they didn't like it and came back to Sudan, like my cousin, he couldn't find a job and was feeling like doing nothing here". (Interview with Sara, 27 years old)

From the encounters and conversations, it emerges that the emotional responses are incredibly varied. Some women express a sense of defeat and resignation, while others feel a profound sense of anger and a desire for revenge against the forces that pushed them to leave. There is also a strong sense of nostalgia, particularly for those who left family members behind in Sudan. But it's not just nostalgia— it's also a deep struggle, a push to not let the circumstances define them. They are not only surviving but trying to rebuild control over their lives in the face of displacement and ongoing war. The future seems to be a major point of uncertainty. Some people talk about returning to Sudan, but there's a sense of hopelessness in their words. They often say, "When it's safe to go back." But for many, there's a recognition that the political situation isn't likely to improve anytime soon, which forces them to reconsider their plans. Some are exploring other destinations, other countries in Africa, maybe Europe. It is evident how these plans change rapidly over time, and how much of it depends on their social networks and access to work and services.

"There is a huge difference between men and women coming here. Our men don't like to spend too much time in the apartment with women, they go outside to drink jabana (coffee) with friends, but here they don't have anything to do. More women came here after the war, also Egypt made it easy for them to come but put a visa for men, they have to pay, before there was kind of free movement among Egypt and Sudan, now it is different. Social life is nice here, there are a lot of cafes, you can meet your friends outside home, you can drink alcohol, in Khartoum you don't have a lot of places. Here (Cairo) is very alive, with music, many programs, and a lot of choices. I think here women adapt better than men, because they build their community, in every neighbourhood they gather, or do whatsapp group 'faisal women' and they communicate, help each other, share resources, sometimes they meet for friendly moments". (Interview with Amira, 22 years old).

As the fieldwork evolved with a better knowledge of the context and informants, one aspect that has begun to emerge with increasing significance is the role of family ties and parental dynamics in shaping the gendered nature of migration. There is an intricate web of relationships that forms, sometimes over vast distances, with varying degrees of responsibility and emotional burden placed on family members who remain behind or who are left to fend for themselves in a new country. In most cases, the family has been divided since it was not safe to travel for some, it was too expensive to travel together, or they didn't want to abandon the country in difficult times. Additionally, someone often stayed to protect property. Families, especially those divided across different societies, are compelled to adapt to new circumstances and challenges in the diaspora. Women are taking on new roles and serving as central solidarity figures

within their families, work environments, and in the community at large. However, this shift is not without its difficulties, as traditional gender roles often clash with the realities of life in exile. A key element of the talks was the neighbourhood of Faysal in Cairo that has become the main hub for Sudanese refugees. The women in this community, many of whom are navigating their own trauma and loss, have formed networks of support and businesses that are allowing their survival and wellbeing. The findings underscore the critical role of solidarity, particularly among women, in helping their community to navigate the challenges of exile.

PRELIMINARY CONCLUSIONS AND REMARKS

This paper has argued for the necessity of integrating a gendersensitive perspective into the study of solidarity within unauthorised migration. By comparatively examining women's experiences across different stages of mobility—those who remain in their countries of origin, those in transit, and those living in displacement—the analysis has demonstrated how gender shapes the forms, meanings, and functions of solidarity in migration processes. It has often been argued in research that women undertaking unauthorised migration are exceptionally difficult to approach, and it has been noted that they often have no information to offer, as a male member (son, husband, distant relative) typically makes decisions throughout the group's journey (Dimitriadi, 2017). In contrast, the present research has sought to give their voices direct visibility, without an intermediary filter, thereby lending dignity to their own experiences and narratives. The decision to focus solely on initiatives and networks established by migrant women is no coincidence; civil society and grassroots organisations play ambivalent roles: while they can foster feminist solidarity and resistance, they may also reproduce bureaucratic or exclusionary practices, especially when coopted by state agendas (Sauer et al., 2019; Di Matteo, 2024).

Feminist theorisation of solidarity across different geographical locales accounts for the experiences of those excluded from defined social groups, including refugees, migrant workers, ethnic minorities, and various categories of dispossessed (Cheah, 2006; Federici, 2012; Fotaki, 2019; Mohanty 1998).

Solidarity emerges from the interplay of material conditions, affective ties, and gendered power relations, linking everyday practices of support to broader structures of inequality and control. In contrast to utilitarian and economic approaches, as well as idealistic but abstract invocations of solidarity, feminist thinking focuses on situated practices and embodied experiences (Covi, 2016; Fotaki & Daskalaki, 2020; Kennu & Fotaki, 2015). In this sense, solidarity is based on shared learning, mutual accountability and continuous engagement with power dynamics rather than on the oversimplified notion of universal sisterhood (Dinçer, 2025; hooks, 2000).). As stated by Dinçer (2025), solidarity practices among refugee/migrant women prompt us to consider the feminist potential of these practices and redefine what feminist solidarity means in contexts of displacement and violence, thereby dismantling the assumption that all refugee women are the same and constitute a homogeneous, united category. Each empirical case revealed a specific articulation of agency, showing how women mobilise care, justice claims, and mutual support to navigate and contest the structural constraints imposed by border regimes and social hierarchies. For example, solidarity among migrant women can manifest as care work and mutual support (as among the Persianspeaking women), and justice claims (as for the Moroccan women), but may also be marked by ambivalence, competition, and shifting power dynamics within and across transnational families and communities, as exemplified by the Sudanese diaspora in Egypt.

Far from being passive followers of their husbands, fathers or brothers, many women, who are rendered invisible by racialised discourses, lead lives that are real examples of the multifaceted

strategies of determination and agency that women on the move are capable of. The evidence from Greece and Egypt demonstrates that migrants and their immediate networks engage in a range of everyday practices of cooperation, which enable them to withstand structural violence and criminalisation. These forms of ‘subaltern solidarities’ – as theorized by the SolRoutes colleagues – are not spectacular; rather, they are pragmatic, embodied, and relational. They can be categorised as infrapolitical acts, that is, acts that are not necessarily politicised in themselves, but which open up spaces for political imagination and manoeuvre. Saba Mahmood's (2005) critique of the idea that agency is synonymous with resistance is particularly pertinent in this context as she argues that agency should be understood as an embodied, relational and contextspecific capacity, rather than being automatically aligned with overt acts of opposition. Applying this insight to migration contexts highlights forms of migrant agency that may not appear “political” or “resistant” at first glance from a Western liberal perspective. Practices such as caregiving, exchanging information, collective waiting, and religious engagement can be meaningful modes of survival and selfformation. Mahmood’s contribution thus expands the vocabulary with which we can interpret the everyday actions of migrant women, which are often dismissed as passive, apolitical, or lacking in resistance. Similarly, Asef Bayat’s work on ‘quiet encroachment’ (2010) provides a complementary framework that captures how migrants engage in incremental, everyday acts that subtly reconfigure their social and spatial environments.

At the same time, however, the depiction of the woman emancipated through migration fails to acknowledge the ambivalence and intricacies inherent in migratory processes, which, on occasion, result in the rediscovery of identities that are, at times, contradictory in nature. The Moroccan case explicates how border disappearances trigger complex processes of gender negotiation, in which gendered familial identities become both resources for and products of political mobilisation. By occupying public space through culturally legitimate positions of care and suffering, women who are still in Morocco open new possibilities for political action while exposing the profound consequences of border violence. The demand for truth thus emerges as a process that collaterally restructures the gender structures governing both intimate life and political participation in Morocco.

Despite the divergent perspectives employed in the case studies, they collectively facilitate a reflection on the gendered implications of the border and its management. Rather than viewing borders as merely territorial lines or institutional regimes, feminist geopolitics, for instance, conceptualises them as instruments of power that engender subjectivities, lived, everyday spaces continually enacted through encounters at checkpoints, in detention centres and shelters, and within the domestic sphere (Pain & Staeheli, 2014). These border spaces are formed through interactions involving fear, vulnerability, caregiving, surveillance and protection, each of which is profoundly shaped by gendered and racialised power relations. For example, women and LGBTQ+ migrants are often exposed to a greater risk of sexual violence, intrusive scrutiny and paternalistic humanitarian approaches, whereas migrant men may be perceived as security threats or as less ‘deserving’ of care (Canning, 2019; Squire, 2011). Through the examination of the available examples, it is evident that the actors under consideration have all endeavoured to challenge and resist these mechanisms, thereby engendering new forms of politicised subjectivities.

From a theoretical standpoint, the paper advances an understanding of solidarity as a *relational and socially embedded practice* rather than a purely intentional or ideological stance. It highlights how solidarity emerges from the intersection of material conditions, affective ties, and gendered power relations, thereby linking microlevel practices of everyday support with broader configurations of structural inequality and control. Methodologically, the study contributes by adopting a multiscalar and comparative approach that connects sites often analysed separately—countries of origin, transit zones, and spaces of settlement—illustrating how forms of solidarity circulate, transform, and persist across borders and temporalities.

In this sense, our outcomes align with the proposal of *infrastructuring solidarities* offered by colleagues working within the same research projects. While most scholars analyse the infrastructures of migration as techniques of governmentality, our perspective focuses on the infrastructures from below – the relational, affective, and material assemblages through which migrants and allies reappropriate the means of movement and transform control into cooperation. These practices give rise to new political spaces and infrastructures of dissensus, wherein the actors involved collectively experiment with alternative ways of organising social life, care, and resistance (Agustín & Jørgensen, 2021). In the absence of formal protection, women rely on these fragile yet resilient relations that sustain the right to resist, claim justice, move, and reorganise their lives in displacement.

REFERENCES

- García Agustín, Ó., & Jørgensen, M. B. (2021). On transversal solidarity: An approach to migration and multiscalar solidarities. *Critical Sociology*, 47(6), 857-873.
- Arendt, H. (1958). *The human condition*. University of Chicago Press.
- Auyero, J. 2020. *Patients of the State: The Politics of Waiting in Argentina*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Bayat, A. (2013). *Life as politics: How ordinary people change the Middle East*. Stanford University Press.
- Biondi, M. (2025). *Mothers raising struggle of Moroccan Families for the New Left Political Prisoners and the Victims of Enforced Disappearance (1972–2005)*. In STUDI MAGREBINI 23.1 (20 25) 65–97.
- Boss, P. (2009). *Ambiguous loss: Learning to live with unresolved grief*. Harvard University Press.
- Bonnin, Ivan, Enrico Fravega, and Luca Queirolo Palmas. 2024. "Of Land and Sea. 'Interested Solidarities' and the Migration Industry from below." *Mondi Migranti* 2: 159–89.
- Butler, J. (2015). *Notes toward a performative theory of assembly*. Harvard University Press.
- Canning, V. (2017). *Gendered harm and structural violence in the British asylum system*. Routledge.
- Cavounidis, Jennifer. 2003. "Gendered Patterns of Migration To Greece." *Επιθεώρηση Κοινωνικών Ερευνών* 110 (110): 221–38.
- Conlon, D. 2011. "Waiting: Feminist Perspectives on the Spacings/Timings of Migrant (Im)Mobility." *Gender, Place & Culture* 18 (3): 353–360.
- Cuttitta, P. (2025). Autonomous Migrant Mobilisations in Libya and (Counter) Externalisation: Transnational Spatial Configurations of Solidarity. *ACME: An International Journal for Critical Geographies*.
- Di Matteo, C. (2024). Debordering and rebordering practices at the intersection of gender and migration. A multisite exploration of specialized services for migrant women experiencing violence in Italy and Sweden. *Critical Social Policy*, 45, 301 - 323. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02610183241262782>.
- Dinçer, C.G. (2025), *Navigating Borders, Cultivating Solidarity: A Feminist Perspective on Iranian Refugee Women's Solidarity Practices in Turkey*, presented at the SolRoutes Intermediate conference (2427/11/2025).
- Edkins, J. (2011). *Missing: Persons and politics*. Cornell University Press.
- Ferrándiz, F., & Robben, A. C. G. M. (Eds.). (2015). *Necropolitics: Mass graves and exhumations in the age of*

human rights. University of Pennsylvania Press.

Hooks, B. (2000). *Feminism is for everybody: Passionate politics*. Pluto Press.

Hyndman, J., and W. Giles. 2011. "Waiting for What? The Feminization of Asylum in Protracted Situations." *Gender, Place & Culture* 18 (3): 361–379.

Huttunen, L. (2025). *Missing persons, political landscapes and cultural practices: Violent absences, haunting presences*. Manchester University Press. <https://doi.org/10.7765/9781526177049>.

Huttunen, L., & Perl, G. (2025). *An anthropology of disappearance*. (Afterword by A. C. G. M. Robben). Berghahn Books. <https://doi.org/10.3167/9781805390725>

Kovras, I., & Loizides, N. (2011). Delaying truth recovery for missing persons in Cyprus. *Nations and Nationalism*, 17(3), 520–539. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.14698129.2009.00437>.

Mahmood, S. (2005). *Politics of Piety: The Islamic Revival and the Feminist Subject*. Princeton University Press.

Menin, L. (2017). *A life of waiting: Political violence, personal memories, and enforced disappearances in Morocco*. In: Nikro, N., Hegasy, S. (eds) *The Social Life of Memory*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.

O'Donnell, S., Ridgway, A., & Borges Jelinic, A. (2025). Ubiquitous waiting: migrant women, temporariness, and waiting as an affective atmosphere. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 51(19), 4821–4840.

Pain, R., & Staeheli, L. (2014). Introduction: Intimacygeopolitics and violence. *Area*, 46(4), 344–347.

Richards, J & Lundahl, G. (2021). *Care to wait*. In Khosravi, S., *Waiting- a project in conversation*. Bielefeld: transcript, 2021, p. 3349.

Robins, S. (2022). The affective border: Missing migrants and the governance of migrant bodies at the EU's southern frontier. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 35(2), 948–967. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jrs/fey064>.

Sauer, B., & Siim, B. (2019). Inclusive Political Intersections of Migration, Race, Gender and Sexuality – The Cases of Austria and Denmark. *NORA - Nordic Journal of Feminist and Gender Research*, 28, 56 - 69.

Squire, V. (Ed.). (2010). *The contested politics of mobility: Borderzones and irregularity* (Vol. 87). Routledge.

Zia, A. (2019). *Resisting disappearance: Women's activism and the politics of memory in Kashmir*. Zubaan Books.

SOLROUTES

The logo graphic for SOLROUTES consists of three overlapping, rounded, wave-like shapes in shades of grey, positioned below the text.

Station 5.
*De-borderlands:
naming, gendering,
infrastructuring
freedom of movement.*

WORKING PAPERS

INFRASTRUCTURING

INFRASTRUCTURING SOLIDARITIES

Enrico Fravega, Rassa Ghaffari,
Ismail Oubad, Federico Rahola,
SOLROUTES Research Collective

INTRODUCTION AND GENEALOGIES

Across the diverse geographical contexts considered by the SOLROUTES project, such as the Mediterranean and the Aegean and their continental extensions – Europe, Africa, Asia - solidarity has become a crucial lens through which to understand the intersections between border governance and migrants' mobilities and autonomy strategies. Within the project, the notion of *infrastructuring solidarities* is conceived as an invitation to rethink solidarity not as a moral virtue or humanitarian response, but as a material and relational practice, a set of dynamic, distributed, and often invisible practices through which people collectively construct, maintain, and transform the social, temporal and spatial conditions of mobility under restrictive and violent border regimes.

The term “infrastructure” has gained significant relevance recently within border studies and migration studies; scholars such as Walters (2015), Tazzioli (2019), Heller and Pezzani (2014), and others have collectively demonstrated that the border functions as a complex infrastructural apparatus, comprising technologies, logistics, and administrative devices that shape both movement and its containment. These studies reveal how infrastructures mediate the exercise of power and visibility, producing a spatial and affective order of mobility.

Our proposal of *infrastructuring solidarities* converses with, but also moves beyond, this literature: while these scholars analyse the infrastructures of migration as techniques of governmentality, our perspective focuses on the infrastructures *from below* — the relational, affective, and material assemblages through which migrants and allies reappropriate the means of movement and transform control into cooperation. These practices create new political spaces and infrastructures of dissensus, where migrants and allies collectively experiment with alternative ways of organising social life, care, and resistance (Agustín & Jørgensen, 2020).

In this sense, *infrastructuring* means privileging the process over the structure, the relation over the object. It describes the continuous, and mostly invisible labour through which migrants and their allies interweave networks of support, gain access to resources, and raise new forms of political presence. These networks do not exist apart from conflict (and borders); rather, they are formed within spaces of exclusion, segregation, and oppression, within and against the border regime, and within broader structures of racial capitalism. (Robinson, 1983) that organise mobility and immobility. As Scheel (2013:279) argues, “that autonomy does not refer to a quality inherent to migratory practices, but to the institution of a relation of irreconcilable conflict between migration and the attempts to control and regulate it by migrants’ practices of appropriation of mobility and other resources”. Rather than reducing solidarity to moral intention or a cultural disposition, this conceptual framework focuses on how solidarities are materially built. That is, on the infrastructures that sustain them, giving them rhythms and direction, as well as the politics of their reproduction. *Infrastructuring* thus captures the collective labour of “making things together,” of building the conditions for movement, life, and resistance in the absence (or hostility) of formal institutions, that is autonomously.

The concept of *infrastructuring solidarities* emerges at the intersection of several critical genealogies in migration, border studies, urban studies, and political theory. From the perspective of autonomy of migration (Papadopoulos and Tsianos, 2013; De Genova, 2017; Scheel, 2013), migration does not arise from structural constraints but rather precedes institutional control and is an ongoing social movement that

constantly reshapes borders and citizenship. This approach shifts the analytical focus from control to capacity, from the state's management of mobility to migrants' autonomous practices of movement and selforganisation. As Papadopoulos and Tsianos write, the "mobile commons" is the space where migrants collectively generate infrastructures of knowledge, care, and connection that both sustain mobility and exceed governmental capture.

Yet, as Queirolo Palmas and Rahola demonstrate (2020), autonomy must be understood not as pure freedom from constraint, but as a practice of inhabiting and traversing the migration routes to and across Europe—that is, the hidden infrastructures through which mobility persists despite repression. Their ethnographic work, uncovering a continent crisscrossed by *subterranean solidarities* (informal networks of cooperation, shelter, and transmission that connect cities, borderlands, and camps into a clandestine infrastructure of endurance), shows the existence of an alternative cartography, composed by "secret passages", collective actions, and dispersed complicities, against the backdrop of the spectacular visibility of the European border regime. For the authors, these "underground infrastructures" are not marginal or residual but constitutive of Europe itself. They expose the dependency of European space on the very mobilities it seeks to contain. Their analysis foregrounds the material and affective infrastructures (houses, cell phones, roads, rumours, and friendships) that sustain movement in conditions of criminalisation. In this sense, their work offers an indispensable bridge between the autonomy of migration perspective and the emerging focus on infrastructuring: it brings attention to the *micropolitical labour* of maintenance, care, and risksharing through which solidarity materialises.

The notion of the *underground* (that is, this idea of an underground infrastructure) resonates with AbdouMalik Simone's one of *people as infrastructure* (2004). In both cases, infrastructure is not a static system but a relational capacity; an assemblage of people, materials, and knowledge that continually reorganises/recomposes itself. Simone's analysis of urban life in Johannesburg, where residents sustain collective functioning through improvisation, parallels the selforganisation of migrants and solidarity actors across the routes leading to Europe: both illustrate how infrastructure is an embodied social process that turns fragility into a resource.

At the same time, *infrastructuring solidarities* draws inspiration from abolitionist thought, especially Harsha Walia (2021) and Ruth Wilson Gilmore (2022). Walia's insistence that *border abolition in practice* entails creating autonomous infrastructures of care and mobility situates solidarity within the politics of dismantling racial capitalism. Gilmore's concept of *abolition geography* – her claim that "freedom is a place" – offers a spatial perspective on this transformation. For Gilmore, *abolition* means the reorganisation of land, labour, and social relations in ways that sustain life. Through this lens, *infrastructuring solidarity* is a form of abolitionist placemaking, a process of constructing geographies of freedom within and against the architectures of confinement.

Parallel to this, the notion of infrastructuring solidarities can be read through a decolonial lens. Following de Sousa Santos (2015), this perspective implies a "*sociology of emergences*", that is, an epistemological and political stance oriented towards recognising and nurturing the still latent possibilities that dwell in subaltern experiences and practices. Rather than viewing these practices as residual or incomplete, the sociology of emergences calls for an attention to the *notyet* — to the prefigurative, fragmentary, and experimental forms of knowledge that arise within the struggles for survival and dignity. As Mignolo and Walsh (2018) remind us, decolonial thought requires an act of *epistemic disobedience*: a refusal to accept Eurocentric hierarchies of knowledge and being. Seen from this angle, *infrastructuring solidarity* is not only a social or political process but also the key to accessing a different epistemic perspective, as it produces knowledge from below that challenges the border as an epistemological device, dividing who can know, who can move, and who can act from those who cannot. Solidarity practices among migrants and other social actors are not simply acts of charity or humanitarianism; they can be transformative, generative, and prefigurative.

However, it is crucial to consider that solidarity within migration contexts does not always emerge as an overtly political or consciously oppositional act. Instead, it is frequently revealed through the context of

ordinary interactions and contingent realities of movement, displacement, and survival. Whilst a significant corpus of scholarship on solidarity emphasises deliberate forms of resistance and structured mobilisation, a growing body of research highlights the spontaneous and nonprogrammable nature of everyday practices of mutual aid, care and cooperation, similar to Asef Bayat's theorisation of "quiet encroachment of the ordinary" (2010); despite the absence of explicit political articulation in these practices, they constitute crucial infrastructures of support that enable mobility, protection, and endurance under conditions of uncertainty and constraint (Snel, Bilgili & Staring, 2020; Della Porta & Steinhilper, 2020). Many of the ethnographic data collected by the SOLROUTES researchers consist of examples of "infrapolitical" acts, which are neither political nor politicised in their aims but can open up space for political imagination and action. It is more common than not that solidarity networks are unstable and not institutionalised; they are dynamic assemblages that respond to moments of rupture, crisis, or opportunity. The operation of these networks is characterised by improvisation, experimentation, and adaptation, which are activated in response to specific contingencies and often deactivated when risks or repression intensify. Such solidarities are not coherent or continuous; rather, they are fragmentary and provisional. Nevertheless, they constitute essential infrastructures of endurance that facilitate mobility in the face of exclusionary regimes of control (Vitturini, 2024).

Taken together, these genealogies converge on a shared intuition: that the border is not merely a site of control but a laboratory of social invention. From Mezzadra and Neilson's notion of *border as method* to Queirolo Palmas and Rahola's *underground Europe*, from Simone's *urban relationality* to Gilmore's *abolition geography*, each perspective highlights the generative dimension of struggle, focusing on how people continuously produce new worlds in the interstices. Within the SOLROUTES theoretical perspective, the notion of *infrastructuring solidarities* foregrounds the practical, embodied, and affective labour through which migrants and their allies assemble the infrastructures of movement and endurance.

The concept of *infrastructuring solidarity* is thus conceived as an invitation to consider border zones as sites of invention, where social relations, material resources, cultural, and political imaginaries are continually congealed and moulded through encounters and manifold forms of solidarities. Within the SOLROUTES project, we assume that solidarity is a recursive social practice of constructing, maintaining, and transforming the relational, spatial, and temporal conditions that make movement, survival, and resistance possible along migration routes. We draw from a double assumption. First, contemporary border regimes cannot be properly understood without examining the material and affective infrastructures that are challenging them. Secondly, solidarity itself is increasingly infrastructural. It flows through a multiplicity of social networks (both digital and nondigital), relying on and joining multiple types of material and immaterial resources, shaping spaces and places, and unfolding over multiple temporal rhythms/cycles.

Accordingly, we elaborate on two distinct types of solidarity (providing solidarity with two further qualifications), talking about *subaltern solidarities* and *abolitionist solidarities*. The first refers to the practices of everyday life and the mutual support that migrants and their immediate networks develop under conditions of structural constraint. The second relates to forms of political counterconduct aimed at abolishing, challenging, or replacing the securitised infrastructures of border governance. Yet, these two forms of solidarity rarely appear in isolation; rather, they overlap, coexist, and shift from one another.

While this distinction is not exhaustive – for instance, it does not encompass the whole repertoire of humanitarian gestures and their ambivalent effects – its analytical potential is far from negligible. Precisely because it does not work as a dichotomic distinction but as a sort of guidance tool for reading solidarity processes and practices, this conceptual articulation has the unsettling potential to illuminate migrants' agency in its multifarious aspects and circumstances, revealing the *situated tactics* through which they try to circumvent the *EUrope's* exclusionary and racializing border assemblages, while also exposing the frictions, contradictions, and asymmetries that such tactics inevitably entail. In that way, it helps us see: a) how forms of cooperation that often remain below the threshold of visibility (shared

spaces, information relays, rotating funds, adhoc shelters, affective alliances) do not simply “assist” mobility but compose, temporary and reversible, infrastructures that reorder space, time and social relations; b) how solidarity practices openly challenging states’ superordinate role, open up new spaces of possibility, and serve as laboratories for the development of manifold social alternatives.

Still, despite their differences, their complex interplay opens unprecedented spheres of autonomy at the material, social, and political levels.

SUBALTERN SOLIDARITIES

Within this broad framework, subaltern solidarities form the foundational layer of *infrastructuring solidarities*. They are the everyday, often invisible, practices of cooperation through which migrants and their immediate networks endure structural violence and criminalisation. Subaltern solidarities are not spectacular; rather, they are pragmatic, embodied, and relational in nature. The term is rooted in the Gramscian vocabulary; it refers to “subaltern subjects” as those who are outside the structures of political representation and cultural hegemony, thus subject to the initiative of hegemonic classes, lacking not only material power but also the means to make their voices heard within dominant cultural and political institutions. Additionally, it refers to the significance of “subaltern studies”, which focus on the autonomous, fragmentary, and often silenced forms of agency, consciousness, and collective life that emerge among the dominated groups, and show methodological and epistemological commitment to conceive history and social theory “from below,” recovering the experiences and practices of those whose presence has been effaced by both colonial and nationalist narratives.

Across SOLROUTES ethnographic field sites, *subaltern solidarities* manifest in multiple forms, namely: **a)** the mobilisation of economic capital; **b)** the mobilisation of social capital; **c)** the production of space; **d)** the conversion of cultural/professional capital into economic capital; **e)** the repurposing of existing networks.

Subaltern solidarities are sustained through the creative mobilisation and conversion of different forms of capital (economic, social, symbolic, and professional) into resources for mobility, endurance, and collective reproduction. In conditions where institutional support is absent or hostile, these forms of capital do not preexist as static assets. Still, they are *socially produced* through everyday practices of cooperation, care, trust, and risksharing. Drawing on a Bourdieusian perspective, economic capital here encompasses not only money or material assets but also the capacity to access and circulate resources through extended kinship networks, rotating credit systems, and informal economies that span multiple spatial and temporal scales.

a) The mobilisation of economic capital (resourcing)

In Senegal, Mauritania, or Morocco, for example, the practice of mobilising economic capital manifests in various forms, such as *tontines*, mutual financing, and the income savings derived from precarious labour in agriculture, fishing, or mining, to sustain journeys toward the EU. These microeconomies demonstrate migrants’ capacity to generate infrastructures of mobility outside formal institutions, embodying the paradox of subaltern solidarity: they both enable emancipation from immobility and reproduce internal hierarchies and inequalities within migrant collectivities. Within this framework, it is worth noting that trustbased microeconomies give rise to specific practices *interested solidarities*. That is, a set of social practices that reveal the spurious status of solidarity, often intertwined with material interests. These practices are configured both as constitutive of a social bond and as a capacitative resource, strategically enabling individuals to resist hostile contexts and dynamics of violent racialization (Bonnin, Fravega & Queirolo Palmas, 2024).

ROUTES	SOLIDARITY PRACTICES
THE EGYPTIAN CROSSROAD	Palestinian exiles in Cairo managed to flee Gaza by drawing on personal/family savings, as well as some forms of “crowdfunding” spread through social connections abroad (average cost: \$ 5,000/Hala company), highlighting the role of class dimension, which is worth exploring here as elsewhere.
THE ATLANTIC WESTMED PASSAGES	<i>Tontine</i> system for the departure financing
THE ATLANTIC WESTMED PASSAGES	Raising money to finance journeys working in specific sectors (gold mining/fishing industry)
THE ATLANTIC WESTMED AND THE CENTRAL MEDITERRANEAN PASSAGES	Raising money to finance journeys working in agriculture
THE AEGEAN BALKANS PASSAGES	Women are becoming economically relevant actors to raise money to continue the journey.
THE EUROPE INNER CIRCULATIONS	Transforming situated knowledge of routes and bordercrossing facilitators into capacity for intermediation. Accumulation of resources to pay for one’s journey through intermediation.

b) The mobilisation of social capital

Alongside economic resourcing, the *mobilisation of social capital* provides the connective tissue of these solidarities. Within precarious border zones, social relations of kinship, friendship, religion, or professional affinity constitute infrastructures of circulation, care, and moral economy. Through them, information, shelter, and protection flow translocally, giving material form to what Papadopoulos and Tsianos (2013) describe as the *mobile commons*. In this sense, subaltern solidarities resonate also with Simone’s notion of *people as infrastructure* (2004), as migrants continuously recompose provisional networks of support that sustain life amid volatility and repression.

These infrastructures are both pragmatic and affective: they rest on trust, reciprocity, and empathy, producing moral economies of belonging and collective obligations. In a sense, collaboration and cooperation practices serve as a platform enabling social and economic reproduction. Thus, transforming precarious encounters into forms of productivity and resilience. Along this vein, Lancione and McFarlane’s (2016) notion of *inframaking* highlights the interstitial labour and affective atmospheres through which marginalised subjects continually remake the city. Through acts of maintenance, repair, and improvisation, people at the urban margins transform fragmented and often failing systems into provisional networks of survival and sociability. These processes, situated between material infrastructures and lived experience, point to the generative potential of relational practices that sustain life beyond the formal architectures of governance. Still, trust, reciprocity, empathy, and care do not merely sustain exchange; rather, they constitute moral economies of belonging and mutual recognition through which solidarity becomes actively (and affectively) lived as well as charged with ethical values. These affective investments can transform networks into collectivities of reciprocal obligation, particularly under conditions of displacement and vulnerability. Social capital thus materialises as an embodied and emotional infrastructure of solidarity, where affective labour contributes to the production of agency and attachment. Within this framework, social capital must be intended as something which is continuously produced and reconfigured through movement itself. Each border crossing, each act of cooperation, transforms the topology of the network, embedding new actors, affective relations, and moral obligations. The social capital, therefore, is not only a means of mobility but a product of mobility. In conclusion, through the mobilisation of social capital, migrants construct viable social worlds within hostile environments, translating interpersonal trust and relations into a logistical

capacity. In the absence of formal protection, it is these fragile yet resilient relations (invisible to any institutional gaze) that sustain the right to move. Yet, as feminist and intersectional perspectives remind us, social capital is neither neutral nor evenly distributed; national, religious or clan belonging, gender, or generational hierarchies often delimit who participates in solidarity and who remains excluded from it.

ROUTES	SOLIDARITY PRACTICES
THE ATLANTIC - WESTERN MED PASSAGES	Grief activism (concerns the families of those involved in shipwrecks).
THE CENTRAL MEDITERRANEAN PASSAGES	"Blackness" as a social resource / Black solidarity
THE EUROPE INNER CIRCULATIONS	Conversion of associative capital and networks to negotiate relocation after encampment expulsion /mobilisation of allies from local authorities to prevent expulsion
THE AEGEAN BALKAN PASSAGES	Networks of former migrants create spaces of socialisation and the spread of information about the journey for current people on the move.

c) The production of space

Subaltern solidarities also materialise through the *production of space*. Migrants reconfigure the environments they traverse – such as borderlands, camps, urban peripheries, and digital spaces – into provisional habitats and logistical hubs. Echoing Lefebvre’s (1974) understanding of space as a social product, these spatial practices can be considered as forms of tactical infrastructuring. Indeed, the transformative power migrants exercise over the landscape (e.g., the reuse of abandoned buildings or camps, the creation of ghettos, or the animation of digital platforms) is not based on longterm forecasts and investments, but rather on tactics to meet immediate needs and their combination with affordances, that is, action possibilities offered by the material environment (Gibson 1986). Examining our ethnographic materials, we noticed that the creation of spaces for encounter, exchange, and shelter occurs in both the physical and digital spheres, defining multiple spaces of “autonomy within control” (Mezzadra & Neilson, 2013) where the social and material conditions of reproduction and mobility are collectively negotiated.

From a relational perspective, space is constituted by interrelations, trajectories, and multiplicities (Massey 2005). Accordingly, migrants’ squats, informal housing practices, as well as the message platforms and social media channels they use to exchange information, services, and practices, give shape to unprecedented relational geographies. Thus, generating alternative spatial orders that challenge the fixity of borders and national belonging.

Concretely, the *production of space* involves a multiplicity of gestures of care, conviviality, and repair that transform inhospitable terrains into inhabitable spaces. These actions are emblematic of what Lancione (2020) defines as “radical housing”, in which dwelling can become a form of political imagination and counterbehaviour that fundamentally rejects the idea of a superordinate spatial order. In this sense, the production of space, which we have considered one of the practices in which “subaltern solidarity” is embodied, can also be seen as a point of contact with the practices of “abolitionist solidarity”.

Similarly, within the blurred space between these two forms of solidarity, Arabic- and Persianspeaking virtual platforms function as solidarity infrastructures in the Mediterranean and Aegean contexts. These platforms enable migrants to navigate routes, find information, evade law enforcement, and access services. These networks are intricate entities, and although most of their users do not actively seek them, driven by explicit political motivations, they are nevertheless structured by a combination of political, ethical, and economic factors (Oubad & Ghaffari, 2025; Ghaffari, 2025).

Ultimately, through this lens, space emerges as both the medium and the product of solidarity: a terrain continually reassembled through the recursive interplay of movement and stay, care and exchange.

ROUTES	SOLIDARITY PRACTICES
THE EGYPTIAN CROSSROAD	The Gazawi community recreated a “New Gaza” through the opening of dozens of restaurants and shops. Producing space is both a form of resourcing migration and sumud. Reproducing a cultural landscape as a form of ethnic/cultural solidarity (?). *
THE CENTRAL MEDITERRANEAN PASSAGES	Creation of a counterinfrastructure of houses, ghettos, and camps to resist deportation
THE ATLANTIC WESTMED AND THE CENTRAL MEDITERRANEAN PASSAGES	Creation of ghettos as: spaces of containment/occultation of migrant presence, operational hubs for the circulation of hyperexploitable labour force, and reproductive space where multiple forms of solidaritybased economies take place
THE AEGEAN - BALKANS PASSAGES	Creating alternative physical and digital spaces to exchange information, services, and practices
THE EUROPE INNER CIRCULATIONS	Creation of alternative translocal circuits of dwelling despite the continuing dispersal of makeshift encampment

d) The conversion of cultural/professional capitals into economic capital

A further dimension is the **conversion of cultural/professional capital** into economic capital. Migrants creatively transform embodied knowhow, technical, artisanal, or maritime, into infrastructures of movement and survival. These transformations are not merely adaptive strategies but acts of epistemic and economic resistance, exemplifying what de Sousa Santos (2015) defines as the creation of value and meaning from below, through subaltern knowledge and creativity.

This is the paradigmatic case of fishermen along the coasts of Senegal and Mauritania. As European and Asian corporate fishing fleets exhaust entire coastal ecosystems, displacing artisanal fisheries and contributing to the spread of poverty among coastal communities, local Senegalese and Mauritanian fishermen have progressively reoriented their expertise toward the “migration industry from below” (Bonnin, Fravega & Queirolo Palmas, 2024). This happens through the conversion of their *habitus* of maritime work (navigation skills, knowledge of tides and currents, boat maintenance, etc.) into an infrastructure of transoceanic mobility. Accordingly, pirogues, once used for artisanal fishing, become vectors, while fish markets and shipyards serve both as logistical nodes and camouflage for illicit activity.

An analogous process has occurred in the Sfax region (Tunisia), where blacksmiths and welders repurposed their technical skills to build tobà (iron boats), which is the common maritime means of transport for subSaharan migrants across the central Mediterranean route. Thus, entering the informal migration economy.

ROUTES	SOLIDARITY PRACTICES
TTHE ATLANTIC WESTMED PASSAGES	The fishing infrastructure in Senegal and Mauritania is being converted for migration. For example, Senegalese fishermen become captains and organisers of journeys across the Atlantic Ocean to reach the Canary Islands. Departures are camouflaged within fish markets and shipyards. It is a form of economic resistance against the global fishing industries’ extractivism, as well.
THE CENTRAL MEDITERRANEAN PASSAGES	In Tunisia, during the decade 20112021, fishermen converted their maritime professional skills from the fishing industry to supporting migratory projects along the Strait of Sicily. More recently, the diffusion of iron boats (tobà), involved the same transformation for blacksmiths and welders.

e) Repurposing of existing networks

Finally, *subaltern solidarities* rely on the **repurposing of existing networks**. Being them religious, civic, or associative, they are all strategically reoriented to sustain mobility and care. These examples, drawn from our ethnographic fieldwork, reveal the plasticity of social capital, which migrates and evolves alongside the people who “inhabit” it. They constitute what Levitt and GlickSchiller (2004) define as transnational social fields: overlapping circuits of relation that sustain life, belonging, and struggle beyond national borders, and of material, affective, and epistemic practices through which migrants collectively reproduce life under constraint, transforming dependence into capacity and exclusion into new forms of social invention.

ROUTES	SOLIDARITY PRACTICES
THE ATLANTIC WESTMED PASSAGES	Murid houses give shape to a network of safe houses for Muslim migrants.
THE EGYPTIAN CROSSROAD	Associations created and run by the Palestinian community to provide assistance and mutual aid with the external help of Egyptian or foreign activists
THE EUROPE INNER CIRCULATION	Repurposing existing civic housing networks from localities to translocal connections to support movement

ABOLITIONIST SOLIDARITIES

Abolitionist solidarities crystallise when migrants and allies collectively refuse the legitimacy of the border regime and act to dismantle it through practice. Across the migration routes, they take various forms, including autonomous search and rescue missions, information infrastructures, sanctuary networks, and political collectives.

Indeed, through the notion of **abolitionist solidarities**, we aim to expand the analytical scope of *subaltern solidarities* by introducing a distinctly political (and decolonial) dimension. If *subaltern solidarities* described the everyday social practices through which migrants mobilise economic, material, social, and cultural resources to endure and move within severe border restrictions (and externalisations), and violence, *abolitionist solidarities* articulate these practices within a perspective which is collective and political, affecting (and contesting) the legitimacy of borders themselves. In other words, *abolitionist solidarities* encompass those solidarity practices directly challenging the racialised and necropolitical EU (b)ordering regime, claiming the abolition of the border as a structure of domination (Walia, 2021).

Within the SOLROUTES analytical perspective, they can be conceived as practices of coresistance, in which migrants and their allies enact alternative infrastructures of movement, care, and belonging, outlining a set of alternative postborder futures.

Operationally, **abolitionist solidarities** draw on: **a)** the creation of autonomous infrastructures; **b)** political resistance and tactical alliances.

a) The creation of autonomous infrastructures

Abolitionist solidarities can arise from the **creation of autonomous infrastructures**. This is the case with the civil fleet in the central Mediterranean Sea, or the pivotal role of information platforms (such as Marino Dubois or the Aegean Boat Report). A wide range of experiences share a common trait: they are all constructed from below and challenge the states’ monopolies directly.

The civil fleet in the Central Mediterranean conducts autonomous SAR (search and rescue) operations that challenge both the racialization of the sea and the criminalisation of solidarity at sea, as operated by states (Fravega & Anderlini, 2025, forthcoming). Their presence reclaims the Mediterranean as a common space of mobility and care rather than a frontier of death (Heller & Pezzani, 2014).

In parallel, information infrastructures from below, such as Marino Dubois' Facebook page, for the central Mediterranean Sea, and the Aegean Boat Report website, for the Aegean Sea, or informal digital networks created by people on the move themselves, reveal the opacity of pushback practices and deaths at sea, while producing forms of counterinformation that highlight and undermine the violence of border apparatuses, both along the EU borders and in third countries.

The informal communication networks linking El Hierro and Senegal, which monitor and report the departures and arrivals of pirogues, also operate as informative infrastructures that challenge the state's dominance in the field of information.

In summary, the creation of autonomous infrastructures does not aim to assist migrants' movements along the routes merely; rather, it openly contests the ambiguous role of the State in providing help, support, and information, while hindering care, racialising space, and undermining solidarities.

ROUTES	SOLIDARITY PRACTICES
THE CENTRAL MEDITERRANEAN PASSAGES	The civil fleet is implementing autonomous SAR activities, thereby opposing the racialization of maritime space highlighted by legislative measures that hinder rescue at sea for migrant boats.
THE CENTRAL MEDITERRANEAN AND THE AEGEAN - BALKANS PASSAGES	Information infrastructures are being created from below (Marino Dubois, in the central Mediterranean Sea, and Aegean Boat Report, in the Aegean Sea; informal digital networks created by POM themselves)
THE EGYPTIAN CROSSROAD	The Gazawi community recreated a "New Gaza" through the opening of dozens of restaurants and shops. Producing space is both a form of resourcing migration and sumud. Reproducing a cultural landscape as a form of ethnic/ cultural solidarity (?). *
THE ATLANTIC WESTERN MED PASSAGES	Murid houses are a network of safe houses for Muslim migrants.* Creation of an informal communication network allowing the reporting of leaving and arriving pirogues

b) Political resistance and tactical alliances

Within the framework of abolitionist solidarities, **political resistance and tactical alliances** represent the explicitly confrontational face of solidarity practices. In this sense, acts of political resistance act as "infrastructures of insubordination" because they expose, resist, and aim to reconfigure the violent apparatus that criminalises movement and solidarity itself.

In Egypt, the mobilisations in Cairo against Israel's genocidal war on Gaza exemplify how abolitionist solidarities exceed the national frame. International and local activists converged to contest the complicity of the Egyptian state in border militarisation and blockade politics. These protests, occurring in a context where public dissent is heavily repressed, reinscribe the Palestinian cause within a broader Mediterranean geography of resistance. They weave together Palestinian, local and transnational solidarities, translating the ethics of sumud (steadfastness) into collective political praxis.

In Senegal, activists and collectives aligned with the AlarmPhone (AP) network contest the repression of "illegalised" migration and denounce the externalisation of European borders onto African soil. By staging protests, circulating counterinformation, and supporting the families of the disappeared, these activists transform migration from a criminalised act into a legitimate form of political agency.

On the island of Lesbos, abolitionist solidarities assume an intersectional form. Feminist and queer collectives of people on the move (POM) collaborate with local and international activists to create safe spaces of mutual protection and political expression within and against the hotspot regime. These alliances reimagine solidarity beyond humanitarian paternalism, foregrounding shared vulnerability and mutual care as bases for a political claim. Through cultural events, protests, and legal interventions, they enact what Harsha Walia (2021) refers to as border abolition in practice, dismantling hierarchies of citizenship and creating alternative spaces of belonging. Their practices are an example of embodied resistance that politicises the most intimate aspects of life under border control: gender, sexuality, and corporeal safety. *“We are women migrant: do not need men and white volunteers to help us”*.

Finally, across the Belgium–France corridor, the act of sheltering migrants in informal networks of hospitality coalesces an abolitionist subject within the very core of the European Union: civil society actors, local communities, and residents collectively refuse the criminalisation of solidarity.

Together, all these practices articulate a “revolutionary” ethic code questioning not merely the existence of “walls” but the abolition of the social relations that require them.

Across all these contexts, tactical alliances emerge as transversal and situational formations, connecting migrants, activists, residents, feminists, religious actors, and international observers through shared commitments to justice and freedom of movement. They are tactical because they operate within the cracks of repression, deploying flexibility, discretion, and temporality as ways to circumvent control, but they are also strategic, because in that they prefigure new forms of political community, challenging the superior role of the state in defining who “belongs” and who is worthy of protection. Along this vein, Tazzioli (2023, 144145) frames the questions as follows: “Irrespective of intentions, experiments of migrant solidarity, spatial occupations driven by claims for freedom of movement and collective mobilisations in support of migrants might be seen as practices that open and link to transversal alliances that unsettle binary oppositions between ‘migrants’ and citizens”.

These alliances, challenging the criminalisation of migration, enact what Mezzadra and Neilson (2013) describe as the *productive excess of movement* —the capacity of mobility to generate new political subjectivities. Their significance lies not only in what they oppose but in what they build: embryonic and isolated forms of postborder democracy, grounded in equality, mutual aid, and shared risk. As Gilmore (2022) writes, “freedom is a place”: it must be built, maintained, and inhabited. The infrastructures of rescue, care, and information that abolitionist networks create cannot be provisional; rather, they can be conceived as fragments of another world already being made within the old one.

ROUTES	SOLIDARITY PRACTICES
THE EGYPTIAN CROSSROAD	In Cairo, international activists mobilise to challenge Israel's genocidal violence and raise support from the Egyptian population.
THE ATLANTIC WESTERN MED PASSAGES	AP activists resist repression against illegalised migration. Grief activism (concerns the family of those involved in the shipwrecks)
THE AEGEAN - BALKANS PASSAGES	Political collectives of women/queer POM and activists
THE EUROPE INNER PASSAGES	Sheltering ‘transmigrants’ across the BelgianFrench route despite hosts risking trials and legal pursuits for facilitating clandestine migration’ / considering and supporting people on the move as rightbearing subjects despite the border’s framing of them as ‘illegals

SOME CRUCIAL ISSUES

a) *The infrastructuring solidarity continuum.*

The distinction between *subaltern* and *abolitionist* solidarities is merely analytical, not empirical. In practice, different forms of solidarity exist on a continuum. The transition from one to another occurs when the labour of survival becomes selfconscious as political, or when the act of care, or repair, is articulated under the form of a collective right. Accordingly, a kitchen in an informal settlement can be a community centre as well; a clandestine shelter could be a logistical node but also a political resource; a rescue operation is also a public statement of disobedience. This is the subaltern to abolitionist continuum: a movement from necessity to transformation, from being an object to being a subject. This continuum also involves shifts in visibility. *Subaltern solidarities* often rely on secrecy, intimacy, and opacity to be put into practice; abolitionist ones, on the other hand, seek exposure, mobilising visibility as a protection and as a form of political leverage. Yet, both depend on the same networks and affective investments. They are not separate phases but coexisting tendencies within the same social field. Yet, this distinction enables us to move beyond a mere descriptive perspective.

b) *Migration routes as sites of infrastructural invention.*

The comparative reading of the ethnographic cases and theoretical genealogies discussed above demonstrates that *infrastructuring solidarity* is an analytical and political lens allowing us to redefine how we understand both migration and the current border regimes. Migration routes, often portrayed as theatres of unpredictable humanitarian crisis and/or uncontrolled mass movement, emerge instead as a space of continuous interweaving of relations, connections, and multifarious forms of extraction and valorisation of economic, social and cultural/professional capitals; that is, migration routes are sites of infrastructural invention. Within this framework, borders cannot be conceived as mere lines of exclusion, but as terrains where heterogeneous actors (migrants, residents, activists, religious associations, digital networks, and various professional groups) oppose the border enforcement apparatuses, while assembling, disaggregating, and recombining relational infrastructures of mobility, survival, and care.

c) *Abolitionist infrastructures.*

Many scholars (Bonnin et al., 2024; Oubad & Ghaffari, 2025; Dadusc & Mudu, 2020) have demonstrated that infrastructures are not merely neutral material supports, but rather social and affective networks deeply entangled with power, temporality, and care. They are not mere backdrops of social life but its very condition of possibility. Countering a scholarship focusing merely on the border enforcement apparatus and the material and immaterial markers it imposes on border zones (Fravega, 2025 – forthcoming), by introducing the notion of *infrastructuring solidarities*, the SOLROUTES theoretical framework foregrounds both the invisible and distributed labour of maintenance, repair, and care that underpins mobility and a political stance claiming for mobility justice. Most significantly, women often play a crucial role in these networks. Ruth Wilson Gilmore's (2022) notion of *abolition geography* is particularly relevant here. To him, abolition was not the negation of the world but its remaking; that is, the construction of life-sustaining geographies that oppose the racial capitalist order. Similarly, Walia (2021) emphasises that border abolition entails creating autonomous infrastructures of mobility and care that make freedom materially possible. Seen through this lens, *infrastructuring solidarity* embodies an abolitionist project: it is about building "freedom as infrastructure."

d) *A new standpoint.*

The politics of infrastructuring solidarities operates in the interstices and in the frictional spaces, in what Papadopoulos and Tsianos (2013) call "spaces of transit," where mobility and immobility are constantly

renegotiated. It works through practices, which are temporary, partial, and fragile, nonetheless entailing a profound reorientation of political imagination. The theoretical and political contribution of infrastructuring solidarity lies precisely in this shift of perspective. It is conceived as an invitation to scholars to see solidarity as a chance to inaugurate a new lexicon for migration studies, one that moves beyond the humanitarian and securitarian paradigms, and a conceptual framework that takes into account de Sousa's (2015) lesson on the sociology of emergences; that is, the need to recognise the embryonic, underrecognised forms of practices and knowledge construction that prefigure alternative futures. In this sense, infrastructuring solidarities enact a decolonial epistemology of the border, focusing on hidden signs, latent potentials and possibilities. These are often overlooked as they represent emerging futures—earlystage possibilities that are usually discounted because they are still in their early form and not yet fully visible, at least from the perspective of the white, wealthy, European subject.

BRIDGING INFRASTRUCTURING, NAMING AND GENDERING SOLIDARITIES

Trying to build some conceptual bridges and a common framework bridging multiple outcomes and ethnographic materials, dealing with the crucial dimensions, chosen to advance and circulate a new understanding of solidarities, two main issues are raised: **a)** the infrastructuring power of words; **b)** gendering solidarities as an intersectional practice.

a) The infrastructuring power of words.

Words, as well as sounds, music and other expressive forms act as means of attribution and circulation of meanings. Migrants' cultural repertoires and productions, starting from their multilanguage vocabularies (but extending to the whole panoply of expressive forms), can be understood as *infrastructuring cultures*. They are cognitive/interpretive devices through which migrants give meaning to the processes, contexts, and practices that shape their material conditions of life along Europe's shifting and violent frontiers. They are the ways through which they make their experiences intelligible, transforming suffering, displacement, and struggle into shared terms and concepts, and thereby making them circulable. At the same time, words and cultural expressions can be considered as revelatory devices of peculiar social positioning and subjectivities. On the one hand, they make visible how migrant subjects situate themselves within and beyond the symbolic and spatial order imposed by nationstates and the EU border regime. If modern social theory has long conceived society as a bounded "container," roughly coinciding with the national space and culture, diasporic and migrant vocabularies radically subvert this assumption. The words emerging from border zones do not speak from within the nation, but from its edges and cracks; through a hybrid wording, mixing languages and creating new words from scratch, they articulate a transnational positioning: the standpoint of oppressed, racialised, and excluded minorities. On the other hand, in doing so, they also reveal the emergence of a moving *subaltern culture* struggling to name the world from below (and from an emic perspective); that is, to build a lexicon adequate to the lived realities of mobility, precariousness, and endurance across the exclusionary borders. Along this vein, language serves as a laboratory for experimenting with alternative grammars of belonging, challenging the Westphalian conception of space and subjectivities. In a sense, words become places of encounter, "provisional commons" where alternative collectivities and imaginaries of *wenneses* can take form. Words, songs, poems, and oral narratives function not merely as reflections of experience but as technologies of relation, infrastructures that connect dispersed life experiences, bridge temporalities, and sustain forms of solidarity that are simultaneously material, affective, and epistemic. In this sense, migrant vocabularies are crucial for understanding how meaning itself travels and how metaphors operate as mobile assemblages through which social worlds are composed and contested. Still, the diasporic vocabularies circulating across migrant routes are neither unified nor stable. Each word brings its own geography of circulation, as well as its own temporality of resonance. The same term or symbol may appear and disappear, or acquire divergent, even contradictory (enantiosemic) meanings depending on context and usage.

Yet, it is precisely in the heterogeneity and instability of these language fragments that we can gain a proper understanding of the shared positions, experiences, and social conditions of people on the move. Seen through this lens, words are a crucial means to express a condition of possibility. They generate the interpretive frameworks through which migrants' collective life and social conditions can be imagined, narrated, and thus maintained across manifold experiences of movement, deportation, violence, and resistance. We call, then, for a methodological attention to the *aesthetic and linguistic labour* that sustains solidarity: the poetics and semantics through which new worlds are named, grounded, and made intelligible against the silencing force of the border.

b) Gendering solidarities as an intersectional practice.

The question of gendering solidarity intersects with the framework of *infrastructuring solidarities* in at least two distinct, yet interrelated, ways. First, it touches upon the material and spatial dimensions of migration routes, questioning how space is produced, policed, and inhabited through gendered and sexualised measures. The notion of *safe spaces* for women and queer people, for instance, foregrounds the politics of protection. Still, it also raises questions about visibility and collective care within the violent geographies of the current border regimes. Yet it is also an invitation to reflect on the very *form* of the border and on the productive effects it acts in shaping the figure of the "ideal migrant." In this sense, the militarisation of border zones, through fences, armed surveillance, maritime control, etc., demands the possession of a specific corporeal capital (physical strength, endurance, and the capacity to confront danger, etc.). This corporeal capital effectively selects and privileges certain migrant profiles while excluding others, thus reinforcing gendered and generational hierarchies of mobility. In this perspective, the border is not a neutral line of passage but a site of biopolitical selection that reproduces gendered and racialised asymmetries within the very process of movement. However, migrants themselves have been observed to develop practices and techniques that actively subvert these dynamics. Informal digital networks and chat groups, for instance, facilitate the exchange of information regarding the physical conditions required for border crossing, the sharing of advice on equipment, medicines and strategies for endurance, and the cultivation of collective intelligence that challenges the selective logics of the border regime. These infrastructures of care and knowledge, facilitated by peers, not only serve to mitigate the violence associated with border militarisation but also reveal the capacity of migrants to reconfigure mobility through solidaristic, situated, and inventive practices. This is particularly true for women, who are often the most active in seeking tips about safety, available resources, and potential risks in both digital and physical spaces of exchange. Their sustained engagement not only reinforces collective preparedness but also foregrounds gendered forms of care and vigilance within migratory networks.

Secondly, *gendering solidarities* raises critical questions regarding the gendering of social practices within migrant networks and solidarity infrastructures. It draws attention to the affective and reproductive labour that sustains collective life under conditions of precarity. In this respect, the concept of *affective infrastructures* becomes crucial, as it refers to the networks of care, emotion, trust, and embodied support that make solidarity a lived social practice possible. These affective infrastructures are not supplementary to political or logistical infrastructures; they are the connective tissue through which many forms of cooperation are materially and emotionally produced. Feminist scholars (Kofman, 2016; Federici, 2020; Tronto, 2020; Mora, 2025) have demonstrated that the politics of care and reproduction are inseparable from the politics of emancipation, while Gilmore (2022) highlighted that "freedom is space". Following this line of thought, gendering solidarities means acknowledging that what sustains movement and resistance is often a scarcely visible, and gendered, labour of maintaining and repairing social relations.

Finally, the perspective we refer to as *gendering solidarities* acts as a **vector of an intersectional perspective**, providing a critical lens through which to interpret the multiple and overlapping axes of power that traverse migratory routes. Gender, race, class, age, and legal status intersect across space and time, shaping uneven experiences of mobility and exposure to violence. From this standpoint, *gendering solidarities* becomes not merely an analytical category but a methodological orientation: a way of tracing how solidarities emerge, persist, or fracture across differentiated subject positions and temporal rhythms. It invites us to perceive solidarities not as homogenous or universal but as stratified,

REFERENCES

- Bayat, A. (2013). *Life as politics: How ordinary people change the Middle East*. Stanford University Press.
- Bonnin, I., Fravega, E., & Queirolo Palmas L. (2024). Of land and sea. "Interested solidarities" and the migration industry from below. *Mondi Migranti*, 2, 159189. DOI: 10.3280/MM2024002007
- Dadusc, D., & Mudu, P. (2022). Care without control: The humanitarian industrial complex and the criminalisation of solidarity. *Geopolitics*, 27(4), 12051230.
- De Genova, N. (Ed.). (2017). *The borders of "Europe": Autonomy of migration, tactics of bordering*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- de Sousa Santos, B. (2015). *Epistemologies of the South: Justice against epistemicide*. London: Routledge.
- Della Porta, D., & Steinhilper, E. (2020). Introduction: Solidarities in Motion: Hybridity and Change in Migrant Support Practices. *Critical Sociology*, 47, 175 - 185.
- Federici, S. (2020). *Revolution at point zero: Housework, reproduction, and feminist struggle*. PM press.
- Fravega, E. (2025forthcoming). No more "Mediterranean". Border materialities in the central Mediterranean Sea and their effects on encounters and solidarities. *Mondi Migranti*, 3.
- Fravega, E. & Anderlini, J. (eds.), (2025 - forthcoming). Mare come spazio di conflitto, resistenza, incontro. *Mondi Migranti*, 3.
- Ghaffari, R. (2025). Iranians' Unauthorized Mobility Projects to Europe: Digital Ethnography of Smuggling and Solidarity. *Partecipazione e conflitto*, 18(1), 2844.
- Gibson, J. J. (1986). *The ecological approach to visual perception: classic edition*. Psychology Press.
- Gilmore, R. W. (2022). *Abolition geography: Essays towards liberation*. LondonNew York: Verso Books.
- Heller, C., & Pezzani, L. (2014). Liquid traces: Investigating the deaths of migrants at the EU's maritime frontier. *Revue européenne des migrations internationales*, 30(3), 71107.
- Kofman, E. (2012). Rethinking Care Through Social Reproduction: Articulating Circuits of Migration. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State and Society*, 19, 142 - 162. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxr030>.
- Lancione, M. (2020). Radical housing: On the politics of dwelling as difference. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 20(2), 273289.
- Lancione, M., & McFarlane, C. (2016). Life at the urban margins: Sanitation inframaking and the potential of experimental comparison. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 48(12), 24022421.
- Lefebvre, H. (1974). *La production de l'espace*. Paris: Anthropos.
- Mezzadra, S., & Neilson, B. (2013). *Border as Method, or, the Multiplication of Labor*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Mignolo, W. D., & Walsh, C. E. (2018). *On decoloniality: Concepts, analytics, praxis*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Mora, A. (2025). Women's Labour in Movement. From Servants and Housewives to Racialised Domestic and Care Workers. *Las Torres de Lucca. International Journal of Political Philosophy*. <https://doi.org/10.5209/ltld.95966>.

- Oubad, I., & Ghaffari, R. (2025). The Digital Infrastructures of Illegal Border Crossings: Solidarity Actors and Networks in the Arabic and Persian Speaking Virtual Spheres. *Critical Criminology*, 118.
- Papadopoulos, D., & Tsianos, V. S. (2013). After citizenship: autonomy of migration, organisational ontology and mobile commons. *Citizenship Studies*, 17(2), 178–196. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13621025.2013.780736>
- Queirolo Palmas, L., & Rahola, F. (2022). *Underground Europe*. New York: Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/9783031161513>
- Robinson, C. J. (1983). *Black Marxism: The Making of the Black Radical Tradition*. University of North Carolina Press
- Scheel, S. (2013) Studying embodied encounters: autonomy of migration beyond its romanticization, *Postcolonial Studies*, 16:3, 279288
- Simone, A. (2004). People as Infrastructure: Intersecting Fragments in Johannesburg. *Public Culture*. 16(3): 407 – 429
- Snel, E., Bilgili, Ö., & Staring, R. (2020). Migration trajectories and transnational support within and beyond Europe. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 47, 3209 - 3225
- Tazzioli, M. (2019). *The Making of Migration: The Biopolitics of Mobility at Europe's Borders*. London: Sage.
- Tazzioli, M. (2023). *Border abolitionism. Migrants' containment and the genealogies of struggles and rescue*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Tronto, J. (2020). *Moral boundaries: A political argument for an ethic of care*. Routledge.
- Vitturini, E. (2024). Solidarities on the move between the Horn of Africa and Italy: Somali migrants' disconnection and networking practices in the 2010s. *Journal of Eastern African Studies*, 18, 97 - 116
- Walia, H. (2021). *Border and rule: Global migration, capitalism, and the rise of racist nationalism*. Chicago: Haymarket Books
- Walters, W. (2015). Migration, vehicles, and politics: Three theses on viapolitics. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 18(4), 469488

SOLROUTES

GENOA
24 - 27
NOVEMBER
2025

INTERMEDIATE
CONFERENCE

Station 5.
*De-borderlands:
naming, gendering,
infrastructuring
freedom of movement*

***BOOK of
ABSTRACTS***

SOLROUTES

The logo graphic consists of three overlapping, rounded, wave-like shapes in shades of grey, positioned below the text 'SOLROUTES'.

Station 5.
*De-borderlands:
naming, gendering,
infrastructuring
freedom of movement*

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

NAMING

Presenter(s): **Angela Curina**
Email: angela.curina@edu.unige.it

INVISIBLE SOLIDARITY IN THE REGIME OF DISAPPEARABILITY: EPISTEMIC AND NEOCOLONIAL VIOLENCE IN DIASPORIC MOVEMENTS FROM SENEGAL

[ABSTRACT]

With this abstract, I propose some reflections on the relationship between the invisible solidarities surrounding illegalized departures from Casamance (Senegal) and the necropolitical framework (Mbembe, 2016) of the «spectral objectivity of capitalist culture» (Taussig, 1993) in which these departures are embedded. By “invisible solidarity”, I refer to the magical practices performed by communities before, during, and after taking the pirogue. In a context where shipwrecks, death, and ghosts are ordinary presences (Queirolo Palmas, Rahola, 2025), this ordinary violence suggests that «there is something to do» (Gordon, 2022). The regime of disappearability (Laakkonen, 2022) not only produces the conditions for a “visible invisibility,” where individuals are constantly subjected to «[the] threat of dying without anyone knowing it» (ibid), but also establishes a regime of suspicion (Sayad, 2002), with the aim of identifying “potential migrants” by various actors. While some studies have emphasized the importance of «consider mystico-religious influences on migrants’ imaginaries and how they understood and analysed risk, their own fate, luck and what actions needed to be taken to mitigate risk» (Deshingkar, Gueye, 2022), I will instead focus on the relations of power in which such cultural practices are inscribed, and on the gap produced by the dialectic of visibility and invisibility in the regime of disappearability.

In this framework, magical practices surrounding departures will be viewed – following De Martino’s (2002) perspective – as «an organic system of vital defence techniques [...] against the risk of not being in the world at those critical moments of existence in which that civilisation feels that history is protruding» (ibid, p. 111). Thus, the analysis moves away from the realm of belief and into the realm of practices of reintegration, resubjectivation and agency in a renewed necropolitical order where extroversion of desire (Mbembe 2018) and colonization of the imaginary (Gruzinski, 1994; Mbembe, 2024; Xavier, 2018) are means of the epistemic violence (Spivak, 2004) and of the capitalistic – and perhaps European – witchcraft (Pignarre, Stengers, 2016).

The starting point, therefore, will be some ethnographic notes on practices heard during a brief period of fieldwork in Senegal, which hinted at the presence of magic in departure rituals. For this reason, these reflections are not intended to be exhaustive, but rather preliminary lines of investigation to frame cultural practices, which in this case have to do with magic, within a broader political-economic context. Magic and magical objects will be considered as strategies and instruments of agency, although included within an economy of solidarity in the regime of (im)mobility. How can communities deal with a history that is protruding? What kind of solidarity (and whose) can be visible, and what kind, instead, must remain interstitial in order to exist?

[BIO]

Angela Curina is a PhD student in Social Sciences at the University of Genoa. She has worked on Moroccan diaspora and post-colonial migration. She currently deals with medicalization and prisons looking through the intersections of care and control policies and epistemologies and watching the mobility of bordering and othering. On this topic, she worked in Italy, France, Morocco and Bolivia, using methodologies from anthropology and critical pedagogical theory. With the ERC SOLROUTES research group, she works on the Atlantic route, solidarity and the relationship between visibility, invisibility and necropolitics.

Presenter(s): **Camilla Macciani**
Email: c.macciani@gmail.com

TAKING SOUTHERN ITALY'S RURAL INFORMAL SETTLEMENTS AS A STANDPOINT TO EXPLORE THE MULTIFARIOUS MEANINGS OF MIGRANT SOLIDARITY

[ABSTRACT]

In the past decades, following the progressive influence of post-colonial studies on scholarly research on migration (Mellino 2012, Mezzadra 2008), words and expressions commonly used to describe migration have been reconceptualized to better grasp the experience of people on the move and overcome the methodological nationalism characterizing migration studies (Casas Cortes et al. 2014). As part of this debate, the multifaceted meaning held by the concept of solidarity has been explored, suggesting the use of an “uneasy” definition of solidarity, going beyond its moral conceptualization (Bonnin et al. 2025). This perspective calls for a stretching of the meaning of solidarity in order to also include actions and figures that, while central to the infrastructure of unauthorized migration, do not operate following a purely altruistic drive. While this framework has primarily been used to explore the experiences of migrants in transit, its theoretical relevance also extends to interpreting the experiences of ‘settled’ migrants living in areas characterized by postcolonial fractures.

Building on five years of ethnographic and militant research in Borgo Mezzanone and Torretta Antonacci, two of Italy’s largest rural informal settlements, the present paper intends to contribute to this debate by exploring the ambivalent and multifarious meanings of solidarity in the context of migrant farmworkers’ rural informal settlements. While not located on a geographical border, these settlements configure themselves as an “agricultural frontier” part of the borderland (Fravega and Queirolo 2022), sharing many similarities with border zones, both in terms of infrastructures of control, segregation and racialization, as well as in terms of practices of resistance, self-organization and solidarity.

The present contribution suggests investigating the ambivalence inherent to informal settlements as being at the same time places of exploitation and refuge, by exploring the multiple and contrasting ways in which they are defined by those who inhabit them. For one thing, looking at naming practices involving the very structure and geography of informal settlements will allow us to go beyond their characterization as “non-places” (Augé 1995), often employed by institutional actors and civil society (Flai-Cgil 2024). For another thing, investigating the discursive practices used by migrant farmworkers to describe forms of solidarity and self-organization taking place in the context of informal settlements will permit further expanding on the idea of “solidarity at large” (Bonnin et al. 2025), while questioning the coloniality inherent to distinctions between supposedly altruistic and “impure” solidarity (ibid.) mobilized by various political collectives, unions and NGOs operating in the area.

[BIO]

Camilla Macciani is a post-doctoral research fellow in sociology at the University of Bergamo. She obtained her PhD from the University of Calabria in September 2024, with a dissertation exploring the forms of oppression and resistance of racialized migrant farmworkers living in the province of Foggia through the lens of racial capitalism. From 2019 to 2024, she has been living in the province of Foggia, where she has conducted her PhD research while actively participating in different ways in migrant farmworkers’ self-organization and contributing to the creation of a legal drop-in centre in the informal settlement of Torretta Antonacci. Her research interests include migration and border studies, agriculture, racial capitalism, and labour studies.

Presenter(s): **Ayoub El Arraf**
Email: aellarraf@unistra.fr

THE WORDS OF EXPERIENCE: GRASPING THE DISCURSIVE DIMENSION OF MIGRATORY ONTOLOGY – THE CASE OF SUB-SAHARAN MOBILITIES IN MOROCCO

[ABSTRACT]

This paper draws on extensive ethnographic fieldwork conducted among Sub-Saharan African migrants attempting to reach Europe irregularly via Morocco. It focuses on the vernaculars developed and mobilized by migrants—their words, discursive practices, and the multiple social and symbolic functions these terms serve. Rather than treating language as a only a medium, the study explores how migrants articulate a migratory ontology through speech: a way of being, sensing, and navigating the world that takes form in and through movement. In doing so, it seeks to illuminate a shared lexicon of mobility—the discursive dimension of their « common mobile » (Papadopoulos & Tsianos, 2013)—emerging from their lived experiences.

This emergent vocabulary operates across several domains: Self-defined identity, which resists the identity-making practices imposed by the state (Bourdieu) and its formal or informal agents (e.g., adventurer vs. illegal). Border-crossing tactics, where terms like pointcheck describe discreet, small-group crossings, in contrast to mass attacks, which involve collective action.

Social relations and their fragilities, reflected in terms like noka, used to name a traitor or someone undermining group solidarity.

Habiting the border, where expressions such as ghetto refer to makeshift homes within informal settlements, while forest or jungle denote the campements themselves.

These terms often originate in West African urban vernaculars but cross linguistic and national boundaries, adapting along migratory routes. They travel with the migrants, structuring and narrating their trajectories. For instance, in southern Morocco, an informal encampment in the desert—later destroyed—was referred to by its inhabitants as the forest...

Born in and through the journey, these words serve emblematic, cryptic, and sometimes ludic functions (Calvet, 2013). They reflect the inventiveness and agency of migrants throughout their passage. Focusing on this vocabulary provides a lens for challenging dominant regimes of control—regimes that often begin with the act of naming itself.

[BIO]

Ayoub El Arraf PhD candidate in sociology, University of Strasbourg Interdisciplinary Laboratory for Cultural Studies (LinCS, UMR 7069) Research interests: Migration, Borders, Makeshift Campements, Critical Border studies, Morocco, Spain, Europe.

Presenter(s): **Irene Peano**

Email: irene.peano@ics.ulisboa.pt

ON BLACKNESS AS METHOD: BROTHER/SISTER-HOOD AND SOLIDARITIES IN ITALY'S ENCAMPMENT ARCHIPELAGO

[ABSTRACT]

The paper will build on thirteen years of engaged research and militancy with and in support of migrants living in Italian agribusiness encampments (with a special focus on the district of Foggia, the Plain of Gioia Tauro and, to a lesser extent, the district of Saluzzo). It starts from a critical appraisal of the use and abuse of the notion and practice of solidarity, in the context of a growing spectacularisation that has invested migrants who live in in/formal settlements (where the boundary between formality and informality is ever shifting and labile). The riots that broke out in the town of Rosarno (district of Reggio Calabria) in January 2010, and the wildcat strike in which over 400 migrant farmworkers participated in the summer of 2011 in Nardò (district of Lecce), brought to light the condition of those living and working in Italy's agroindustrial districts in the new millennium, across national and international arenas.

These moments of collective struggle, and the further experiences of self-organisation to which they gave rise up until the present, have been countered by several attempts to defuse their potential, through initiatives (led by trade unions, NGOs and political organisations) that have denied migrants their subjectivity and autonomy, pitting them as passive victims or, at best, silent followers in moments of spectacularized and pacified denunciation that capitalize on conditions of structural, racist violence. In these cases, when solidarity is flagged it is emptied of its meaning, employed as foil for attitudes infused by paternalism, and manipulated to deflect the radical potential of migrants' anger and frustration, also leading to, or reinforcing, their disillusionment and mistrust towards external subjects claiming to support them. These silencing mechanisms have been reflected also in the lack of recognition of several moments of protest and strike, in which migrants had a leading role, and which I and other comrades have been accompanying since 2012.

Without wishing to exempt these latter processes from criticism and self-reflexivity, I would like to claim an understanding and a practice of solidarity that is based on mutual processes of learning, on radical openness and on the construction of languages and practices of collective struggle that must constantly question pre-conceived interpretations and forms of action. At the same time, building on this notion of solidarity, I want to approach the forms of everyday mutualism that characterize migrants' living and work-spaces across the encampment archipelago through the lens of Blackness as method, as it has been worked through by several thinkers and members of the Beyond Inhabitation Lab, of which I am also a member. Relations of conviviality and support, in the encampment archipelago and beyond, are conceptualised by its inhabitants by means of kin-making (most often as horizontal brother/sister-hood, but at times also marking hierarchies by means of seniority). While never exempt from conflict and sometimes inflected with asymmetries and dependencies, these relations are veritable infrastructures of care unfolding in the interstices of spaces of negation, abjection, inhabitability and segregation operating by means of racist logics. Blackness in this sense does not denote a stable identity but a means of relating and making things possible otherwise, within and against capture.

[BIO]

Irene Peano received a PhD in Social Anthropology from the University of Cambridge (2011). She held post-doctoral positions at the University of Bologna (including a Marie-Curie Intra-European Fellowship) and a

visiting professorship at the University of Bucharest's Research Centre.

For more than 15 years she has been carrying out research on the exploitation of migrant labour, with a focus on sexual and farm work, and on forms of resistance to migration and labour regimes, conducting extensive fieldwork in Nigeria, Italy and Romania. Such research has entailed the active support of collective forms of organisation and struggle.

More recently, she has been researching the genealogies of forms of mobility containment and the development of agribusiness in Italy's agro-industrial districts, by means of in depth archival and oral-history research. She has been assistant researcher at ICS-ULisboa since 2021, after having worked at the same institute as a member of the ERC project "The Colour of Labor: the racialized lives of migrants (led by Cristiana Bastos), since 2017.

Presenter(s): **Joma Thomé**
Email: joma.thome@pm.me

“I am not a migrant, I am discovering and conquering”. ETHNOGRAPHIC INSIGHTS INTO DISCURSIVE PRACTICES OF MAGHREBI MIGRANTS ON THE GREEN ROUTE.

[ABSTRACT]

This paper explores discursive practices and emic vocabularies of speaking about mobility and trajectories from the perspective of harraga (ḥarrāga), North African migrants, along the so-called “Green Route” (the “Balkan Route”) en route to Western Europe. Drawing from multi-sited ethnographic fieldwork, including participant observation and ethnographic interviews in Bosnia-Herzegovina and various European cities, the paper lays out (some of) the meanings harraga ascribe to their journeys by foregrounding their naming practices. Their multi-faceted narratives oscillate between understanding their journeys on a continuum between adventure and horror trip, as well as their roles between international citizens and those who act outside the law. Their naming practices for the “Green Route” are distinctly different from the sea route which is rooted in the natural and geographical difference between both routes, but also in the Maghrebi history of mobility, journeying, and the hijra (religious pilgrimage to Mecca). I argue in particular for drawing on the historical and semantic richness of the term harrag(a) itself which has not been sufficiently explored in academic literature on mobility and migration. Most academic literature places the emergence of the “phenomenon” of harraga in the 1990s or early 2000s (Arab 2007; Pandolfo 2007; Khaled 2013; Mnasri 2023), following the largely presentist bias of framing “irregular” migration towards Europe as a recent “phenomenon”. However, it is important to differentiate that while the naming of harraga/l-hrig (the act of migrating “clandestinely”) established in colloquial Darija in the Maghreb in the 1990s, the practice itself is not new, as shown by M’Charek (2020), Benhadda (2025), and Garnaoui and Sakhi (2024).

The colloquial double meaning of harrag as both the one who is mobile and crosses borders (“the migrant”) and the one who facilitates the act of crossing borders (“the smuggler”) widely expands and goes beyond established definitions and discourses as well as migrant-smuggler dichotomies, and provokes a more nuanced understanding of solidarity, resistance, and agency. In fact, this double meaning offers the potential to open up novel and ethnography-informed debates about mobility and migration beyond narrow epistemological foundations that tend to focus on discourses such as “irregularisation”, “risk management”, and “smuggling victims”.

Further, in this paper, I mobilise the rihla (Ar. journey) as a an ‘infrastructure of imagination’ that not only organises meaning of the migration journey and modes of travelling but also places it in a historical continuity of rihla practices, thus, providing a sort of historical legitimacy. The rihla originates in the practice of travelling from the Western edge of the Islamic umma to the centre and origin of the Islamic religion in the Hijaz area, specifically the cities of Mecca and Medina. As these travellers used to write extensive reports and books about their travels, these developed into its own “travel-writing” genre, the ‘Rihla’, that combines spiritual, educational, and sociological elements, and auto-ethnographic observations. These travels served as a way of connecting with others and Islamic knowledge within the umma, but also to improve one’s self-understanding by understanding the differences between oneself and the others and their practices one encounters during the travels (El Moudden 1990). These ‘Rihla’ texts were “encyclopedic in character” (1990, 74) and provided an astonishing amount of details with the intention to not only share observations and events but also to provide detailed advice for future pilgrims. For instance, knowledge was supplied on ecology, wells as water stations en route, weather conditions, and common practices such as market guides on converting merchandise (including slaves) into coin for purchasing necessary

commodities for the journeys.

By embedding my analysis of current naming practices with historical continuities, and by examining how harraga interpret, navigate, and emotionally engage with the “Green Route”, this article challenges Global North discourses and narratives of travelling, journeying and being mobile, in general, and specifically, the question of who has the right to be mobile and how.

[BIO]

Joma Thomé is a PhD candidate at the Fulda Graduate Centre of Social Sciences, Fulda University. She holds a Master’s in Human Rights (Fulda University), and Bachelor degrees in Adventure Tourism Management (Munster Technological University) and Outdoor Education (Atlantic Technological University). Her doctoral thesis is a multi-sited ethnography on the lived experience of “illegalised” migrants from the Maghreb on the so-called “Balkan Route”. Joma’s research focuses on bottom-up understandings of mobility and migration, critical border studies, border violence(s), biopolitical technologies, and self-organisation practices by “illegalised migrants”. She currently teaches at the Department of Social and Cultural Sciences of Fulda University.

Presenter(s): *Mari D'Agostino*
Clelia Farina

Email: *mari.dagostino@unipa.it*
clelia.farina@unipa.it

NAMING, CONNECTING, MAPPING. CO-CONSTRUCTING MIGRANT HETERO-GLOSSARIES

[ABSTRACT]

This article stems from a long-standing ethnographic engagement initiated in response to the arrival of significant numbers of young migrants transiting along the Central Mediterranean route and arriving in Palermo. Since 2012, thousands of them have joined the classrooms of the School of Italian Language for Foreigners (ItaStra) at the University of Palermo. Within this space of encounter, an ongoing project has emerged, intertwining sociolinguistic research, teaching practice, and social activism.

In its initial phase (2016–2021), which involved hundreds of young Sub-Saharan individuals, shared imaginaries and forms of knowledge emerged strongly—generated and circulated by these young people within and beyond the spaces of ItaStra. The narratives collected—co-constructed in both guided and spontaneous interactional contexts—oppose the dominant discourse on “unauthorized migration” and are rooted in the multilingual resources of our interlocutors, understood not only as expressive tools but as constitutive elements of their counter-narrative power.

Within this framework, using ethnographic methods and open-ended interviews, a set of terms and ethnotexts (cf. Paternostro & Sottile 2010) was collected—focused on spaces of segregation and the actors who benefit from movement along the Central Mediterranean route (cf. D'Agostino 2021). The resulting multilingual glossary originates from oral naming practices across various semantic fields, among which the term *coxeur* is particularly significant. It offers a complex vision of migration that highlights familial and friendship networks, and recognizes the enunciative power of individuals on the move—who resist the dominant narrative that frames migration solely through the lens of organized illegality, structured around binary oppositions such as ‘migrant’/‘smuggler’/‘trafficker’, ‘economic migrant’/‘refugee’ and so on. Over the years, many aspects have evolved—both within the research group (comprising university teachers and Ph.D. students in linguistics) and in the profiles, trajectories, and experiences of those arriving in Palermo. A particularly noteworthy shift occurred in 2021, when Tunisia emerged as a principal country of departure along the Central Mediterranean route. This geopolitical change has reshaped the ecology of mobility and, in turn, the linguistic and discursive landscapes through which solidarity networks and self-organized forms of resistance are constituted. Yet, the relative novelty of this configuration and the lack of comprehensive documentation present specific methodological challenges for the researcher-observer. Parallel transformations have occurred within the national reception infrastructure (the SAI system) and among grassroots actors offering informal support and advocacy.

Against this backdrop, the present contribution seeks to examine emerging naming practices that arise within migrant narratives and interactions, conceptualized as tools for identifying autonomous enunciative spaces and for narrating a reality marked by flux and unpredictability. This focus marks a new phase of research, oriented toward collecting new terms and ethno-texts to capture the specificity of the most recent migratory experiences, in their linguistic, geographical, and social complexity. This is a methodologically dense undertaking, further complicated by the evolution of discursive practices increasingly mediated by digital channels, which generate new communicative contexts, new forms of knowledge, and new connections (cf. D'Agostino & Mocciaro 2021; Farina 2024).

Throughout all phases of the project, ethical/methodological reflexivity as well as an ongoing experimentation of data collection models and tools that also support self-awareness and voice-taking

practices for all participants remains central. In this direction, participatory methods plays a central role—such as language workshops integrating images, speech, and movement—fostering not only linguistic learning/teaching programs but also the reactivation of prior repertoires and resources. Above all, the goal is to create spaces where interaction and listening authentically connect all involved participants and gain the dignity of a social testimony—deliberately subverting contexts in which others decide what migrant people should say, in which language, and with which words.

[BIO]

Mari D'Agostino is Full Professor of Italian Linguistics at the University of Palermo, where she directs the School of Italian Language for Foreigners (ItaStra) and is Principal Investigator of the PRIN 2022 project “Young New Migrants and Italian as a Non-Native Language between Spontaneous and Guided Learning.” Her work addresses theories of linguistic variation, the sociolinguistic repertoire of contemporary Italy, and the documentation of migratory multilingualism. Recent publications include “Sociolinguistica dell'Italia contemporanea” (with Giuseppe Paternostro, *Il Mulino*, 2025) and “Noi che siamo passati dalla Libia. Giovani in viaggio fra alfabeti e multilinguismo” (*Il Mulino*, 2021).

Clelia Farina is a PhD candidate in Linguistics at the University of Palermo. Her research documents both spontaneous and guided learning of Italian as an additional language and the development of reading-writing skills among newly arrived plurilingual young people in Palermo from North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa. Her interests include grassroots writing practices, societal multilingualism, and the theory and practice of teaching multilingual learners with emerging literacy.

Presenter(s): **Paola Gandolfi**
Email: paola.gandolfi@unibg.it

**DOING BARZAKH.
NAMING THE TENSION AND THE SUSPENSION IN
THE BORDERLANDS IN NORTHERN MOROCCO.
An ethnography and an artistic creation contribute
to question on solidarity and freedom of movement**

[ABSTRACT]

The international research project “Houdoud- Frontiers” intends to explore the mobility of bodies, memories and imaginary and aims to create opportunities of dialogue between young researchers in social sciences and young artists in visual arts and performing arts, either from Morocco or from elsewhere but working on contemporary Morocco.

Having participated to the different phases of this project as a member of the scientific committee of Houdoud – Frontiers, but also as a participant observer and a mentor during the workshops, I would like to focus my attention to a couple of projects, the first by an anthropologist and the second by an artist (a theater director and a performer). They both focus on the borderland on the shores of Northern Morocco and they explore, in different ways, the migrants’ daily living experiences, their risks in the border regime, their act of waiting and their original modes of solidarity among them, but also among themselves and the inhabitants. They make us familiar with their words, their idioms and their ways of naming practices, suggesting us how all these can be epistemic traces of solidarity in motion. So, we gradually find ourselves to discover how the mobile subjects define their daily experiences and their trajectories. In the recent years, some of the places from where the migrants try to cross the Mediterranean towards Europe are called Barzakh, a word used in the Coran to evoke a state of transition between death and resurrection, hell and paradise, a sort of limbo, a condition of waiting (Archer, 2017).

Doing Barzakh, Making boza is how migrants name the act of burning the border (Bajalia, 2021, 2023; Maher, 2016). The modes of acting and being in these borderlands (Agier, 2016) are deeply modified by the modes of crossing the spaces in the border, in terms of social spaces and material spaces. Within this framework, both this artistic creation and this ethnography bring us to focus on a relational and processual approach that deeply questions our ways of naming the freedom of movement, borderlands and solidarity. We gradually come to consider alternative infrastructures as battlegrounds where several modes of solidarities and informal networks promoted by migrants are a contestation and a reaction to the border regime; we come to comprehend how solidarity can act as powerful energy opening possibilities and helping to face daily constraints.

Finally, we also question about the importance of approaches anchored to ethnographies and creative and original research formats, as they are able to give voice to the situated knowledge of migrants and to let us come closer to their intimacy, their multiple and hidden languages and their daily practices in the borderlands (Gandolfi, 2025). By doing so, these kinds of approaches appear very precious to rethink critically the ways of naming contemporary mobility, as well as the complex and unfolding nexus between solidarity and freedom of movement.

[BIO]

Paola Gandolfi Associate Professor of Transnational Migrations and Arts, Transnational Migrations and Educational Experimentations, Anthropology of the Arab countries of the Mediterranean, in the Department

of Human and Social Sciences of the University of Bergamo.

Among her many publications, "Noi Migranti. Per una poetica della relazione" (2018); Prefazione a "I sentieri dell'indisciplina" (Ksikes, 2024); "Tra altrove e aldilà: immaginare l'Europa dal Marocco. Regimi di controllo dei confini, movimento di corpi e immaginari mobili "(2025).

Since 2019, she is member of the Scientific Committee of the International Research Project "Houdoud/ Frontieres" Pour une fertilisations des savoirs entre arts et recherche. A research project which consists of fieldworks, international conferences, cultural events and workshops aimed to experiment a dialogue between ethnographical practices and artistic practices. Research item: La mobilité des corps, des memoires , des imaginaires. HEM University of Rabat, University Mohamed V of Rabat, Chair Fatima Mernissi, University of Bordeaux.

Presenter(s): *Sara Bonfanti*
Email: *sara.bonfanti@edu.unige.it*

REFUGEE HOSTING AS RELATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE. NAMING AND NEGOTIATING SOLIDARITY IN FAITH-BASED PRIVATE SPONSORSHIPS

[ABSTRACT]

In recent years, humanitarian corridors have been celebrated as “safe and legal pathways” for refugees in Europe. Yet, beyond policy frameworks, these initiatives—rooted in transnational agreements among Christian organizations (e.g., Comunità di Sant’Egidio, Chiesa Valdese, Caritas, and equivalents in France and Germany)—rely on local relational infrastructures that reconfigure the meaning and practice of solidarity. Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork and in-depth interviews with asylum seekers, volunteer sponsors, and institutional actors across Italy, France, and Germany, this paper explores how “private sponsorship” is experienced and enacted at the micro level.

The analysis focuses on how hospitality is framed not only as a moral duty but also as an affective and bureaucratic practice that both empowers and disciplines. Migrants’ and sponsors’ emic terms for the relationships they build—ranging from “new family” to “moral debt”—reveal tensions between gift and obligation, care and control, solidarity and asymmetry. These findings resonate with Martani’s (2023) critique of hospitality as an ambivalent social bond, and Boccagni’s (2021) notion of “relational infrastructure” as a key analytical lens for refugee reception.

This contribution speaks to both the naming and infrastructuring of solidarity: it examines the moral vocabularies used by different actors and highlights how solidarity becomes embedded in informal but powerful arrangements of care, surveillance, and support. It ultimately invites reflection on the (de) politicising effects of religious and familial framings of refugee hosting.

[BIO]

Sara Bonfanti is a social anthropologist specialized in migration and religion, kinship and care. She conducts multi-sited ethnography with South Asian diasporas in Europe and has recently focused on asylum governance and grassroots hosting initiatives. She collaborated as post-doc fellow within the ERC project HOMInG (2017–2020), contributing to *Ethnographies of Home and Mobility* (Routledge, 2021) and *Finding Home in Europe* (Berghahn, 2023). Currently affiliated with the University of Genoa, and lecturing at the University of Milan, her ethnography bridges academic inquiry, public engagement, and activist scholarship.

Presenter(s): *Sophie Bava*
Email: *sophiebava@yahoo.fr*

LA NAISSANCE D'UN MARCHÉ RELIGIEUX DE LA MIGRATION : ENTRE SOLIDARITÉS, NOUVELLES THÉOLOGIES ET CONTRÔLE.

[ABSTRACT]

Au Maroc, à la suite de l'installation croissante de migrants d'origine subsaharienne depuis les années 2000 et la fermeture des frontières européennes, les organisations confessionnelles ont été redynamisées et les acteurs religieux – en particulier chrétiens – ont endossé de nouveaux rôles.

Ce faisant, ces acteurs ont intégré une véritable « industrie migratoire » et se sont retrouvés dans une position ambiguë : s'ils proposent bien une ressource spirituelle et matérielle pour les migrants, du fait de leur légitimité religieuse, ils peuvent par le choix des programmes de financement participer à renforcer un marché du contrôle, de la sédentarité et du retour dans le gouvernement international des mobilités africaines.

Nous interrogerons la redynamisation du paysage chrétiens du Maroc, les nouveaux acteurs, les formations et toute cette fabrique des solidarités par le bas qui est assez étonnante, au regard du projet religieux et humanitaire plus global du christianisme, et du Maroc au sein du gouvernement mondial (et intra africain) des mobilités.

[BIO]

Sophie Bava is a socio-anthropologist at the IRD, AMU-LPED.

She is Scientific Advisor to the Knowledge Community 'Migrations' to the CEO of the IRD, Coordinator of the Movida International Laboratory, Co-Editor-in-Chief of the journal *Afrique(s) en Mouvement*, and Africa-Mediterranean Project Manager at the SoMuM Institute.

Presenter(s): **Viola Castellano**
Ezgi Güler

Email:
viola.castellano@uni-bayreuth.de
ezgiguler.89@gmail.com

SITUATED SOLIDARITIES AND EPISTEMIC BORDERLANDS: RETHINKING RESEARCH FROM WITHIN THE BORDER REGIME

[ABSTRACT]

This paper interrogates the complex positionalities of precarious researchers working critically on migration management and border externalization from within institutional and national contexts that operate as both internal and external borderlands of the European migration and border regime. In so doing the paper aims to discuss the intersection between knowledge production and solidarity, exploring to which extent the latter could be named and grounded in this standpoint. Scholars in such sites-like Italy and Turkey-are often deeply entangled in the very systems they seek to critique: positioned close to displaced communities and humanitarian infrastructures, frequently engaged in political struggles for freedom of movement, while simultaneously reliant on research economies that extract value, legitimacy, and funding from the governance of migration. As such, our work is shaped not only by proximity to border violence, but also by shared precarity and the epistemic advantages afforded by our location within the academic-migration-industrial complex.

Drawing on some of our respective (auto)ethnographic engagements-one between Italy and the Gambia, examining the post-asylum relationalities and externalization policies; the other in Turkey, tracing the everyday lives of Syrians under temporary protection regime and the pressures of return-oriented rhetoric and policies-we explore how research conducted from these zones of entanglement can offer conceptual insights into the politics of solidarity, without reproducing the hierarchies it seeks to unsettle.

Rather than offering positionality as a confessional reflexive gesture, we use it here as conceptual leverage to interrogate the uneven and complex terrains of knowledge production and the contradictions of solidarity within migration studies. We draw on border as method (Mezzadra and Neilson 2013) to situate our field sites and the multiple ways in which we are implicated in them not just as objects of analysis, but as vantage points from which to retheorize borders as epistemic, institutional, and ethical formations. At the same time, we engage the notion of ethical entrapment to describe how researchers become enmeshed in moral and political tensions that are not fully resolvable through reflexivity alone.

In so doing the intervention wants to take seriously the imperative to center migrant standpoints while simultaneously asking how this centering operates when scholars-especially those located in EU borderlandss-are structurally authorized to narrate, interpret, and mediate migrant experiences in ways migrants themselves often are not. Rather than speaking for or with, we interrogate how scholarly authority is constructed through proximity to migration, and how solidarity itself could become a contested, and potentially troubled scholarly resource.

In reflecting on these epistemic dimensions, we ask what forms of accountable, situated solidarity might be possible for researchers whose knowledge is formed within-yet not reducible to-the logics of the border regime. From our respective positions within Europe's borderlands, we propose a mode of critical engagement that foregrounds entanglement, asymmetry, differential proximity, and the limits of scholarly authority as conditions for rethinking the ethics and politics of migration research.

[BIO]

Viola Castellano is a social anthropologist working as a Senior Research Associate at the Chair of Social and Cultural Anthropology of the University of Bayreuth. Her research interests focus on how inequalities

are reproduced through welfare, asylum and migration policies in the US and Europe and West Africa. Currently she is exploring border externalization in the Gambia working collaboratively with Gambians on the move and conducting a study-up ethnography with European and international organizations. Her publications have appeared in journals as *Anthropological Theory*, *Focaal* and *City and Society*, while her monographic volume was published in 2023 by Berghahn Books.

Ezgi Güler recently received a Junior Fellowship from the Centre of International Excellence “Alexander von Humboldt” at the University of Bayreuth, where she is currently undertaking a research stay. She holds a Ph.D. in Social and Political Sciences from the European University Institute in Florence. Her research interests span urban studies, gender and sexuality, migration, sex work, structural violence, and research methodologies. Her work has been published in *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, *FocaalBlog*, *Palgrave Macmillan*, and *SAGE Publishing*.

SOLROUTES

Station 5.
*De-borderlands:
naming, gendering,
infrastructuring
freedom of movement*

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

GENDERING

Presenter(s): **Agnese Pacciardi**
Email: agnese.pacciardi@svet.lu.se

NEGOTIATING BORDER VIOLENCE: RESISTANCE AND SOLIDARITY IN SENEGAL

[ABSTRACT]

Over the past two decades, Senegal has become a key transit hub for West African migrants en route to Europe. This has prompted intensified migration cooperation between the European Union and Senegal, including the externalisation of European borders through both overt security measures, such as the deployment of Frontex, and more covert strategies involving development projects, humanitarian discourse, and policy frameworks aimed at curbing migration. In response, an increasing number of Senegalese civil society organisations have emerged, engaging with and resisting the shifting landscape of migration governance and humanitarianism.

Drawing on extensive ethnographic fieldwork conducted across Senegal between 2023 and 2024, and grounded in critical border studies and social movement theory, this paper examines two distinct strategies of resistance and solidarity.

It focuses on two civil society initiatives: The Caravan of the Missing and two Women's Collectives.

The former, primarily led by former migrants and male human rights activists, embodies a more masculinist approach to no-border activism, marked by public protest, direct confrontation with state institutions, and demands for accountability from both Senegalese and European authorities. In contrast, the Women's Collectives, formed by mothers and wives who have lost loved ones at sea, mobilise around grief and absence. Their activism often takes place in domestic and community spaces, where private mourning is transformed into quiet yet powerful political action.

By comparing these male-led and female-led initiatives, this paper explores gendered practices of solidarity and resistance in the context of border violence. It offers a theorisation of solidarity that is grounded in lived experience, and that extends beyond overt opposition to state power to include everyday acts of care, endurance, and collective memory. In doing so, it sheds light on the diverse and often overlooked forms of political engagement that emerge at the intersection of migration, loss, and activism.

[BIO]

Agnese Pacciardi is a PhD researcher at the Department of Political Science, focusing on borders, mobility, and security through critical lenses. Her research primarily delves into European external migration management in North and West Africa, exploring the impacts and implications of these policies. Additionally, she is an active member of the feminist collective *Fundación Luvo*, dedicated to promoting emancipatory pedagogies and anti-racism through writing and educational initiatives. Her work has been published in *Geopolitics*, the *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, *Environment and Planning C*, *European Security*, *Critical Studies on Security*.

Presenter(s): *Marzia Bona*
Ida Motteran

Email:
marzia.bona@eurac.edu
ida.motteran@eurac.edu

EVERYDAY SOLIDARITIES AND GENDERED EXPERIENCES OF HOUSING PRECARITY

[ABSTRACT]

For the second conference axis, “Gendering solidarity”, this contribution explores the nexus between housing precarity and the lived experiences of gendered subjects. Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork in a housing facility located in the rural, bilingual, and border region of South Tyrol in Northern Italy, the paper investigates how prolonged uncertainty shapes intimacies and gendered solidarities among cohabiting migrant residents.

We frame housing exclusion as a manifestation of borders’ materiality (Lancione 2023) –persisting well beyond the moment of arrival and formal recognition of status. The case study focuses on a housing facility managed by a social cooperative that occupies a hybrid position in the reception system: neither fully public nor entirely autonomous, it functions as a “third step” in the accommodation pathway. The facility hosts a heterogeneous mix of residents–single individuals, couples, families, older and younger people–who co-manage shared spaces and negotiate rules that diverge from standard institutional reception models. Stays are open-ended and loosely tied to individual “empowerment” projects (Miles et al. 2024), often centred on language acquisition (particularly salient in this bilingual region) and economic autonomy.

Housing precarity extends the temporalities of waiting, foregrounding the multifaceted nature of border and “the intersubjective constructions of internalised boundaries within social contexts” (degli Uberti 2019). In this liminal space (Cacciotti, 2024), distinctions between forced and voluntary migration become blurred (De Haas, 2021), making room for alternative forms of recognition and solidarity to emerge. These may be grounded in shared origins, language, gender, or demographic affinities—for example, solidarity among families sharing childcare responsibilities.

The analysis unfolds along two interrelated strands:

1. Gendered experiences of housing precarity: How do men, women, and families navigate living conditions marked by unclear rules, ambiguous rights, and temporariness? How are caregiving, intimacy, and emotional wellbeing affected by such instability? Particular attention is given to how domestic space can become a site where gendered violence is reproduced, silenced, or resisted.
2. Emergent solidarities within housing precarity: Building on recent literature that questions dichotomies between forced and voluntary migration (De Haas, 2021), the paper explores how shared experiences of waiting foster gendered and relational forms of solidarity. These often take shape through informal support systems based on gender, age, family configuration, or common language.

Methodologically, the study is grounded in immersive ethnographic fieldwork, including a period of residence in the facility, participant observation, and semi-structured interviews with residents, staff, volunteers, and former inhabitants. Enabling methods such as walking interviews and photovoice captured the embodied experience of inhabiting the facility and its rural surroundings. The research adopts an intersectional perspective and critically reflects on the researcher’s positionality, particularly in relation to imaginaries and practices of inhabiting (Veness 1993).

By centring everyday life in a marginal, semi-formal housing setting, this contribution offers insights into how migrants navigate the tension between autonomy and control—and how solidarity becomes both a survival strategy and a mode of resistance in rural peripheries.

[BIO]

Marzia Bona is a researcher at the Institute for Regional Development and the Centre for Migration and Diversities at Eurac Research in South Tyrol, Italy. With a background in political science and human rights, her work focuses on migration, housing, and local development, particularly in rural and mountain areas. She is currently working in the SERIGO project, exploring the role of social and solidarity economy initiatives in addressing housing exclusion among migrants in small and medium-sized towns. Her research adopts an intersectional and ethnographic approach, with a strong focus on place-based experiences, gendered dynamics, and solidarity practices. She is particularly interested in how migrants inhabit, contest, and reshape marginalised rural spaces.

Ida Motteran is a Junior Researcher at the Institute for Regional Development and the Center for Migration and Societal Change of Eurac Research. They studied sociology and political science between Ireland (University College Dublin) and Italy (Università di Trento). Their research focuses on housing rights and the financialisation of social housing, with an intersectional and critical approach to urban and rural transformations. They are also interested in the interrelations between feminism and queer studies and, increasingly, the notion of place-making and public spaces. Ida is now working on the housing access and pathways of people with a migratory background within the HEU project SERIGO.

Presenter(s): **Cemile Gizem Dinçer**
Email: cgdincer@bu.edu

NAVIGATING BORDERS, CULTIVATING SOLIDARITY: A FEMINIST PERSPECTIVE ON IRANIAN REFUGEE WOMEN'S SOLIDARITY PRACTICES IN TURKEY

[ABSTRACT]

Turkey is a signatory to the 1951 United Nations Refugee Convention, but due to its specific 'geographical limitation', it grants refugee status only to asylum seekers from member countries of the Council of Europe. Individuals from non-European countries who apply for international protection are granted only "conditional refugee status", which only allows for a temporary stay in Turkey until their resettlement and restricting their access to basic rights and often leaving them trapped in the country for many years.

Amid this uncertainty, refugee women face gendered violence, exploitation, and everyday bordering practices – yet they also actively cultivate solidarity and resistance.

Building on feminist ethnographic research with Iranian refugee women in Turkey, I focus on their everyday practices and examine how refugee women cultivate forms of solidarity and develop individual and collective tools of resistance under conditions of control, surveillance, and violence. Women continuously navigate, negotiate, and resist various bordering mechanisms in their daily lives to claim their lives.

By linking solidarity with resistance, I argue that these acts of resisting, negotiating, and navigating borders are inherently collective, sustained through solidarity networks they build with one another, grounded in shared knowledge, experiences, and mutual care. Refugee women not only circulate and share existing knowledge but also actively produce new forms of collective knowledge, care, and support.

By centering solidarity among refugee women and approaching it from a feminist perspective, I aim to show how practices of mutual care and solidarity shape and transform the meaning of resistance, agency, and everyday life under bordering regimes.

[BIO]

Cemile Gizem Dinçer Postdoctoral Associate, Boston University, Center on Forced Displacement, Boston, USA. I am a feminist researcher focusing on gender and migration. For over a decade, I have worked on projects related to borders, asylum, and gender, while actively participating in feminist and migrant solidarity groups. I received my Sociology PhD from Middle East Technical University, Turkey, in 2022, and I am currently a postdoctoral researcher at the Center on Forced Displacement at Boston University.

My research interests include borders, deportation, sexuality, migrant labor, and solidarity practices among refugees and activist groups.

My recent work has appeared in *Ethnic and Racial Studies* <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2025.2474620>, where I focus on the waiting experiences of refugee women in Turkey.

Presenter(s): *Ilaria Bilancetti*
Email: *ilariabilancetti@gmail.com*

MOBILITY AS A RESOURCE IN THE TRANSITION TO ADULTHOOD AND A CHANNEL OF INTERGENERATIONAL SOLIDARITY: lights and shadows within Egyptian masculine kin circuits in Milan.

[ABSTRACT]

In Egyptian peripheral areas, the urge for financial security is perceived before the age of legal maturity, as gender norms require young men to carry the costs of marriage and become the family breadwinner. Due to a progressive deterioration of state schools and shortage of rewarding job prospects, early mobility has become for many a resource for the transition into adulthood, a necessary step in the life-cycle and the ultimate strategy for self-realization. Mobile ambitions include intergenerational mutuality, as Egyptian boys' sense of wellbeing is intrinsically bounded with the wellbeing of their parents and siblings. In this context, the prestige deriving from being the migrant of the family and the prime agent of collective upward mobility, represents a decisive motivation for youths to face borders and work hard.

In Italy, Egyptian nationals count by far the highest number of unaccompanied foreign minors (UFMs). Many flee from randomly assigned reception structures and move toward the metropolitan city of Milan, where the largest Egyptian diaspora in Europe resides. There, they can rely on the support of relatives and take advantage of working opportunities within their network of co-nationals. Political discourses concerning migrant minors, tend to undermine the crucial role that families exercise in youths' trajectories -both at the moment of departure and arrival, as the legal category of UFMs is constructed around notions of 'loneliness' and "vulnerability." Foreign minors, for the fact of being 'unaccompanied' by their parents, are not free-roaming children in a foreign country; rather, they may rely on relatives responsible of facilitating their staying and adaptation. Kinship networks abroad are influential and operative before the moment of departure, as they represent a trigger to migration and source of security for families.

The presentation brings the ethnographic case of Egyptian youths who move to Milan to reach their uncles and cousins, after a period of staying in reception structures. Whether relatives function as a source of support or abuse constitute an issue that requires empirical exploration, as kin solidarity holds a controverse nature in migratory contexts: it facilitates information brokerage and recruitment but also the rise of forms of control and exploitation that hide behind false promises and informal agreements. Based on field data, the study confirms that kinship networks provide a dynamic reservoir of material and emotional resources that enable youths' to safely navigate in a foreign country and reproduce a sense of belonging based on shared values. However, it also exposes how kin relatedness generates pressure to comply with families' instructions and conform with culturally situated gender norms. Youths' migratory projects reflect both generational aspirations and family obligations, while diverse trajectories intersect through kin circuits in the practical attempt to meet social expectations of financial success.

By adopting an intersectional approach to mobility, the study sheds lights on the nuances of kins' male solidarity, stressing on the tension between cultural capital and material necessities as potential sources of rivalry, as it generates conflicting positionalities within transnational families.

[BIO]

Ilaria Bilancetti PhD candidate in "Analysis of Social and Economic Processes" at the Department of Sociology and Social Research of the University of Milan-Bicocca. She has an interdisciplinary academic

background in development studies and social anthropology, matured between Italy and the UK. Her early research interests focused on labour and gender in the MENA region, where she lived for some years working for NGOs. She has experience working in the Italian reception system (SAI) and she is currently conducting ethnographic research on Egyptian youths in Milan, with a specific focus on the social role that the Egyptian diaspora exercise on their transitions to adulthood. The research is situated within the field of Youth Studies, adopting a transnational and intersectional approach to mobility.

SOLROUTES

The logo graphic for SOLROUTES consists of three overlapping, rounded, wave-like shapes in shades of grey, positioned below the text.

Station 5.
*De-borderlands:
naming, gendering,
infrastructuring
freedom of movement*

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

INFRASTRUCTURING

Presenter(s): **Chiara Martini**
Email: chiara.martini@unimi.it

EVERYDAY ALLIANCES AND THE MAKING OF SOLIDARITY INFRASTRUCTURES IN THE BALKANS BORDERLANDS.

[ABSTRACT]

The paper examines the relational dynamics within grassroots solidarity initiatives and their role in addressing the violence and fragmentation associated with the European border regime. The analysis focuses on two peripheral yet geopolitically significant border regions, - the Una-Sana Canton in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the southeastern frontier between Bulgaria and Turkey -, and it is based on extended and engaged ethnographic fieldwork conducted between 2022 and 2024, following the trajectories of people on the move across the Western Balkans, along with the networks of solidarity that accompany and support them. It explores how migrants, activists, volunteers, and local organizations interact with and respond to border policies shaped by externalization, structural violence, and the erosion of formal protection mechanisms.

In these sites, institutions are frequently missing, dysfunctional, or openly antagonistic. Against this backdrop, the sustenance and mobility of people on the move increasingly rely on self-organized, people-driven infrastructures of support. These initiatives are rooted in practical support, reciprocity, transversal alliances, and everyday interpersonal relations—emerging as vital alternatives to the violence and abandonment of bordering processes. Despite the growing criminalization of both migration and solidarity, such networks have managed to sustain relational ties across local, national, and transnational spheres—though often under unstable and precarious conditions. These connections foster everyday sustenance and cultivate situated communities built on mutual recognition and shared responsibility, operating independently of institutional frameworks.

Employing AbdouMalik Simone’s conceptualization of “people as infrastructure” (2004), the article reinterprets infrastructure not as static or technical but as relational, mobile, and socio-material configurations essential to daily life. While Simone’s work is grounded in urban contexts—highlighting how those marginalized from the formal economy constitute themselves as infrastructure by navigating complex and shifting urban assemblages—this paper extends the concept to border spaces. In these contexts, the capacity to navigate and negotiate constantly shifting configurations of danger, aid, surveillance, and control is not only essential to everyday sustenance but to mobility itself. The paper argues that in border zones, infrastructures forged through solidarity are not merely supporting structures for surviving abandonment, but dynamic relational mechanisms that enable movement, shelter, information exchange, and protection. This analytical shift from city to border reveals the broader applicability of Simone’s framework to zones of transit, irregularity, precarity, and exclusion.

The analysis places particular emphasis on the interpersonal and inter-group relations that sustain these solidarity practices. Rather than being rooted in shared identities, these ties evolve through interactions among diverse actors navigating violent and exclusionary environments. Following Featherstone (2012), solidarity is understood here as a process of creating connections across difference, often in contingent, improvised, and precarious contexts. Such relational encounters serve not only as mechanisms of support

but as generative spaces where unforeseen alliances and social formations take shape. Therefore, the paper argues that in spaces where mobility is criminalized and access to rights is unevenly distributed, relationships—whether forged locally or transnationally—constitute both the conditions and conduits through which solidarity is enacted. These ties form infrastructural webs that counter fragmentation and challenge prevailing border mechanisms by linking people across differences.

[BIO]

Chiara Martini is a PhD candidate in Sociology and Methodology of Social Research at the University of Milan. Since 2018, she has been engaged in research, activism, and volunteer work in support of people on the move across Italy and the Western Balkans.

Her doctoral project explores bordering processes and grassroots border solidarities along the Balkan Routes, with a particular focus on Greece, Bulgaria, and Bosnia-Herzegovina.

She has presented her work at various international conferences, and her research has been published in several peer-reviewed journals. Her research interests include critical border and migration studies, social movements and solidarity, mobility, and urban studies.

Presenter(s): **Mashudu Salifu**
Martin Bak Jørgensen
Tomislav Pusic

Email: mashudus@ikl.aau.dk
martinjo@ikl.aau.dk
tomislavp@ikl.aau.dk

**BECOMING THE ROAD:
MIGRANT-MADE INFRASTRUCTURES AND THE
CORRIDOR OF VIOLENT TRANSIT.**

[ABSTRACT]

“Sometimes we do not know exactly where we are going—we just move.” These words, shared by Kajaley, a Gambian migrant now living on El Hierro, distil the collective experience of countless others navigating the Western Mediterranean–Atlantic and Balkan migration corridors. These journeys do not follow fixed paths—they are shaped by hunger, prayer, fear, and fragile hope passed by hand across borders and camps. In these fractured terrains, migrants do not just travel; they become the infrastructure of movement itself.

This paper introduces the concept of the Corridor of Violent Transit to understand migration routes from Sudan, Somalia, Gambia, Senegal, Mali to the Canary Islands, and from Afghanistan through Bosnia and Herzegovina to Croatia—not as linear paths but as recursive geographies of abandonment, resistance, and solidarity. Drawing on Mbembe’s (2003) necropolitics, we argue these corridors function as transnational deathscapes, where African, Middle Eastern, and European states co-produce violent spaces—deserts, seas, forests, and detention zones—designed not to welcome or reject but to delay, deplete, and erase.

Within these zones, migrants create survival infrastructures like shared SIM cards, rotating shelters, encrypted voice notes, and boats without captains. These affective, improvised systems are built through collective intelligence as the state withdraws. As Papadopoulos & Tsianos (2013) and Sheller (2018) note, these are paradoxical zones of mobility justice, where autonomy and exposure coexist.

This study employs critical cartography and patchwork ethnography (Günel et al., 2020; Przybylski, 2021), based on fieldwork in the Canary Islands and the Bosnia and Herzegovina–Croatia corridor. It includes participant observation and interviews with migrants, local officials, civil society, and humanitarian workers. In the Canary Islands, we volunteered daily with civil organisations and the Red Cross in registering and transferring irregular migrants from El Hierro to Tenerife. In Croatia, we encountered two silent, shivering minors whom the police had found alone the night before in a muddy forest. Their fathers had left to oppose the violent border and never returned. The children were caught between states, abandoned by policy, and sustained only by endurance. In their eyes, there was no panic, only waiting and waiting for survival.

Narratives like theirs, or Najmudin’s story of crossing the Melilla fence thirty-nine times before taking a cayuco to El Hierro, are not exceptions. Nor is Kajaley’s vow: “If they take me back, I will try again—by boat, by bike, by anything else.” These testimonies serve as living maps—cartographies of refusal, where migrants challenge a violent geography not by remaining still, but by moving repeatedly. They demonstrate how repetition, not resignation, becomes a strategy for survival, and how migrants constantly reconfigure space against a regime designed to erase them. This paper contributes to the SOLROUTES axis on infrastructuring solidarity by demonstrating how migrants resist disappearance through remaking space. Confronting necropolitical borders, they build fragile yet potent networks of solidarity. In this context, survival becomes a form of resistance, and movement constitutes the infrastructure of life.

[BIO]

Martin Bak Jørgensen is Professor in Processes of Migration at DEMOS at the Department for Culture and Learning, Aalborg University, Denmark. He works within the fields of political sociology and political geography. He has published the books *Solidarity Without Borders: Gramscian Perspectives on Migration and Civil Society Alliances* (Pluto Press, 2016) and *Solidarity and the "Refugee Crisis" in Europe* (Palgrave, 2019), both co-authored with Óscar García Agustín. With Carl-Ulrik Schierup he co-edited the books *Politics of Precarity* (2016) and *Contending Global Apartheid* (2022) both with Brill.

He has published articles in journals like *Internal Migration Review*, *Critical Sociology*, and the *Journal of International Migration and Integration*. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0104-8543>

Mashudu Salifu is a PhD Fellow at the Doctoral School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Department of Culture and Learning, Aalborg University in Denmark. He is part of the DEMOS research group and is affiliated with the Enacting Citizenship and Solidarity in Europe "From Below" (ECSEuro) project.

He holds an MA in Culture, Communication, and Globalisation, and an MSc in Development and International Relations from Aalborg University. His research focuses on migration corridors, solidarity infrastructures, and urban responses to global crises. His recent publications include: "From the Ghettos to the Camps: Interrelational Solidarity between Housing and Migration Regimes in Denmark" (with Bernhardt, Buconjic, and Jørgensen) in *Framing Solidarities in Times of Multiple Crises* (Palgrave, 2025), and "Immigrant Inclusion and Municipalism in a Danish Context" (with Martin Bak Jørgensen) in *Cosmopolitan Civil Societies* (2025). These studies examine how municipalities challenge exclusionary national policies by employing municipalism, care, and inclusive citizenship. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9890-7003>

Tomislav Pušić is a PhD Fellow at Aalborg University's Doctoral School of Social Sciences and Humanities and a member of the DEMOS research group, which focuses on studying democracy from an interdisciplinary perspective. His research, situated within the CORRIDORS project, examines migration corridors formed through grassroots solidarity across Eastern and Southeastern Europe.

His ethnographic fieldwork focuses on urban sanctuary and migrant agencies in Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Poland, and Ukraine. He holds an MA in Culture, Communication, and Globalisation, specialising in migration and social movements. <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-5547-1145>

Presenter(s): **Nagehan Uskan**
Email: naguskan@gmail.com

VISUAL INFRASTRUCTURES OF SOLIDARITY: MIGRANT-LED VIDEO-ACTIVISM AGAINST PUSHBACKS IN LESVOS

[ABSTRACT]

This presentation explores how collective video-making can function as a form of visual infrastructure that sustains subaltern and abolitionist solidarities in the context of migration. It focuses on the work of Kino, a grassroots, migrant-led video-activist collective founded in 2018 on the island of Lesbos. As a co-founder and active participant in this collective, I draw on a collaborative and embedded research position that is both methodological and political.

Kino emerged as a response to the misrepresentation and erasure of autonomous migrant experiences within dominant media narratives. By producing and circulating videos grounded in their own perspectives, the collective has sought to build self-organised infrastructures of resistance. Over the past seven years, Kino has produced a series of short films addressing everyday life in Moria camp, women's solidarity in refugee camps, LGBTQ+ migrants' struggles, and the illegal pushbacks in the Aegean Sea. Often silenced or distorted in mainstream discourses on migration, these issues are brought to the fore through acts of visual self-representation.

The presentation focuses specifically on the 2022 short film *What is a Pushback?*, which was produced collectively during the workshop *Visual Storytelling as Resistance on Lesbos Island*, with the participation of migrants, activists, students and NGO workers. The film was created using found footage sourced from dominant frames, surveillance cameras, and media channels and re-assembled through a co-editing process. Narratives for this research were gathered through the audio recording of a semi-structured assembly involving participants who have experienced pushbacks firsthand and engaged in the production process. The workshop and the filmmaking served both as a site of production and a space for political reflection, where participants discussed and redefined the politics of visual resistance and video making as action, in relation to the violence of European border regimes.

This study examines how found footage originating within dominant visual and surveillance frameworks can be subverted and transformed into images of action, through the lens of Farocki's concept of the operational image and Flusser's theory of the technical image. This analytical lens highlights the ways in which grassroots video production can transform visual material into a counter-infrastructure of resistance capable of challenging dominant discourses and producing alternative forms of knowledge and solidarity from below.

[BIO]

Nagehan Uskan is a sociologist, documentary filmmaker, and activist. Her work lies at the intersection of the sociology of film, film as activism, and filmmaking in exile. As a postdoctoral researcher and lecturer, she has held positions at the University of Fribourg, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Off University and İzmir University of Economics. Her scholarly work extends into collective, art-based research projects that use video making as a tool. She is a co-writer of *Multilingual Dictionary: Living Together in a Refugee Camp* and *I Escaped to My Future*, both produced as part of the *Beyond Social Cohesion: Global Repertoires of Living Together (RePLITO)* project supported by Berlin University Alliance. Uskan is also a co-founder and member of Kino, a grassroots migrant video collective in Lesbos Island that has produced various works including *Natives of the New World*, *Khalas (Silence)*, *What is a Pushback?*, and the award-winning *Me Too*. She is currently the project partner of a British Academy project hosted by the King's College London.

Presenter(s): **Spyros Galinos**

Email: sgalinos@cpt.org

INFRASTRUCTURES OF CRIMINALISATION AND THE STRUGGLE FOR SOLIDARITY: MONITORING TRIALS OF ALLEGED SMUGGLERS IN THE AEGEAN

[ABSTRACT]

This paper draws on a trial monitoring project by CPT–Aegean Migrant Solidarity, focused on the systemic criminalisation of refugees and migrants accused of human smuggling in Greece, particularly on the island of Lesbos. Many of those prosecuted—often young asylum seekers—are charged simply for steering boats across the Aegean Sea and face punitive legal proceedings that reflect deeper entanglements between border enforcement, judicial institutions, and deterrence policies.

Conceptualising the Greek legal system as part of the broader migration control infrastructure, the paper highlights recurring patterns of due process violations, inadequate legal defence, and disproportionate sentencing, as also evidenced in recent studies such as *A legal vacuum* (Borderline Europe, 2023).

These legal mechanisms shift the burden of migration governance onto individuals, producing a spectacle of punishment that upholds the EU's securitised border regime while complicating or suppressing expressions of solidarity. We argue that CPT's monitoring practices constitute subaltern solidarity infrastructures: informal, grassroots forms of resistance that confront state violence through documentation, support, and transnational advocacy.

Trial monitoring is framed as a form of abolitionist solidarity—not aimed at reform, but at challenging the legitimacy of a system that criminalises mobility and weaponises legality. Our methodology involves in-person trial observation throughout 2024–2025 in Lesbos and other Aegean locations. Observers attend court hearings, record procedural irregularities, and provide support to defendants and their families, creating counter-infrastructures grounded in presence, witnessing, and resistance.

[BIO]

Spyros Galinos is a researcher-activist based in the Aegean islands, working at the intersection of migration studies, border violence, and solidarity infrastructures. His research explores the full spectrum of migration control regimes—from hard infrastructures such as border policing, detention, and surveillance, to soft mechanisms like the criminalisation of migration through legal narratives and public discourse. He focuses particularly on the evolving border-industrial complex across the Aegean.

His work includes trial observation, critical legal analysis, and community-based documentation of state violence. Spyros collaborates closely with CPT–Aegean Migrant Solidarity, Legal Centre Lesbos, and other transnational networks challenging the EU's securitised migration regime. His academic and activist practice aims to expose and contest the infrastructures of control, while contributing to subaltern and abolitionist forms of solidarity rooted in grassroots resistance and collective care.

Presenter(s): **Jules Soupault**
Email: jsoupault@uvic.ca

THE CRIMINALIZATION OF SOLIDARITY ACROSS THE EUROPEAN BORDER REGIME

[ABSTRACT]

This article discusses the complementarity between the criminalization of solidarity and the “externalization” of European borders. Both have been widely documented and discussed; however, they are often discussed independently. This dislocation can be problematic, for example, when considering how efforts to decriminalize solidarity at the EU level could unintentionally increase the EU’s pressure on non-member states already implicated in the European border regime.

At the same time, scholars working on solidarity and externalization have critiqued the pitfalls of presentism and EU-centrism, calling for contextualizing and situating EU policies in the *longue durée* history of European colonial empires, without denying the agency of the non-European actors in the development and maintenance of borders (Tazzioli and Walters 2019; Cobarrubias and Lemberg-Pedersen 2025; Gross-Wyrtzen and El Yacoubi 2024).

To participate in this discussion, I treated law as infrastructure that shapes both the conditions of mobility and solidarity, and the relations between states. The first dimension refers to how legal infrastructures shape what types of mobility and solidarity are (im)possible, while the latter invites thinking of the circulation of legal frameworks across jurisdictions and their articulation with pre-existing legal structures (Cowen 2023; Raeymaekers 2024; Vergnano 2021).

The findings are based on data from 84 countries that are either EU member states or Frontex “partners.” Though not exhaustive, given that the EU’s border interventions operate beyond Frontex, this selection offers an entry point in a border regime broader than the EU. For each state, I collected the legal provisions that criminalize the facilitation of entry, exit, or stay, along with the relevant exemptions and aggravating factors. These were then organized into sub-categories to enable comparative and relational analysis across jurisdictions.

My contribution is twofold: it allows for mapping out the space in which solidarities are criminalized at the scale of Frontex’s interventions and reveals the dynamic relations across legal regimes within this space. The central argument is that, rather than being in tension or separated, the internal and external logics of the EU’s border regime are interconnected and complement each other. While at the scale of a state, the adoption of exemptions or aggravating factors can be explained by the vitality of solidarity struggles or, conversely, by their repression, having a comprehensive dataset enables a systematic understanding of how the European border regime functions as a whole, and the multi-modal production of infrastructure of border control.

[BIO]

My name is **Jules Soupault** (he/him), I am a PhD candidate at the University of Victoria (Canada) and a research fellow at the Borders in Globalization. My doctoral dissertation aims to examine the politics of abolition in the context of “integrated” borders and the specific obstacles posed by these borders to the possibility of organizing, resisting, and building alternatives to policing, surveillance, detention and deportation. I use a mixed-method approach, which is primarily made necessary by an intention to do non-state-centric research while also avoiding participation in the surveillance of the movements I align with. In addition to the abolitionist literature and critical border studies, I am influenced by critical geography, decolonial theory, and racial capitalism studies, which help me think of the fragmented yet intensely connected spaces of (b)ordering and their history.

[Author Index (A-Z)]

Agnese Pacciardi — Negotiating Border Violence: Resistance and Solidarity in Senegal. [\[Gendering\]](#)

Ayoub El Arraf (SOC) — The Words of Experience: Grasping the Discursive Dimension of Migratory Ontology – The Case of Sub-Saharan Mobilities in Morocco. [\[Naming\]](#)

Angela Curina — Invisible Solidarity in the Regime of Disappearability: Epistemic and Neocolonial Violence in Diasporic Movements from Senegal. [\[Naming\]](#)

Camilla Macciani — Taking Southern Italy's rural informal settlements as a standpoint to explore the multifarious meanings of migrant solidarity. [\[Naming\]](#)

Cemile Gizem Dinçer — Navigating Borders, Cultivating Solidarity: A Feminist Perspective on Iranian Refugee Women's Solidarity Practices in Turkey [\[Gendering\]](#)

Chiara Martini — Everyday Alliances and the Making of Solidarity Infrastructures in the Balkans Borderlands. [\[Infrastructuring\]](#)

Iliaria Bilancetti — Beyond and behind the system of protection for young migrants: alternative solidarity, exploitation ... or both? [\[Gendering\]](#)

Irene Peano — On blackness as method: Brother/sister-hood and solidarities in Italy's encampment archipelago. [\[Naming\]](#)

Joma Thomé — "I am not a migrant, I am discovering and conquering". Ethnographic insights into discursive practices of Maghrebi migrants on the Green Route. [\[Naming\]](#)

Mari D'Agostino, Clelia Farina — Naming, connecting, mapping. Co-Constructing migrant heteroglossaries [\[Naming\]](#)

Marzia Bona — Everyday Solidarities and Gendered Experiences of Housing precarity [\[Gendering\]](#)

Mashudu Salifu, Martin Bak Jørgensen, Tomislav Pusic — Becoming the Road: Migrant-Made Infrastructures and the Corridor of Violent Transit. [\[Infrastructuring\]](#)

Nagehan Uskan — Visual Infrastructures of Solidarity: Migrant-Led Video-Activism Against Pushbacks in Lesbos. [\[Infrastructuring\]](#)

Paola Gandolfi — Doing Barzakh . Naming the tension and the suspension in the borderlands in Northern Morocco. An ethnography and an artistic creation contribute to question on solidarity and freedom of movement. [\[Naming\]](#)

Sara Bonfanti — Refugee Hosting as Relational Infrastructure. Naming and Negotiating Solidarity in Faith-Based Private Sponsorships. [\[Naming\]](#)

Sophie Bava — "La naissance d'un marché religieux de la migration : entre solidarités, nouvelles théologies et contrôle. [\[Naming\]](#)

Spyros Galinos — Infrastructures of Criminalisation and the Struggle for Solidarity: Monitoring Trials of Alleged Smugglers in the Aegean. [\[Infrastructuring\]](#)

Viola Castellano, Ezgi Güler — Situated Solidarities and Epistemic Borderlands: Rethinking Research from Within the Border Regime. [\[Naming\]](#)

SOLROUTES

A graphic element consisting of a wavy line with a color gradient from green on the left to red on the right, positioned below the text 'SOLROUTES'.